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Assessing the Pragmatic Abilities of Algerian Autistic Teenagers

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DEDICATION

I dedicate this thesis to my dear friends, my most precious Asma, my parents, and all of those who trip and fall into the crevices of language, cast outside of its trail.

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Abstract:

This study aims to investigate the pragmatic language abilities of seven Algerian Autistic Teenagers from Oran, Algeria. The study uses a mixed-method approach, relying on thematic analysis to study the data. Autism Spectrum Disorder is a neurodevelopmental condition characterized by difficulties with social interaction , and repetitive, rigid behaviors. Pragmatic ability, a leading element of social interaction, is known to be impaired in autism, causing the autistic individual to experience difficulty with understanding language in social contexts. Several assessment methods have been developed to measure pragmatic competence in ASD, testing different aspects of pragmatic ability to provide a clinical profile for the autistic person, including standardized evaluation tests. A pragmatic assessment test, which takes into consideration the landmark concepts of pragmatic ability, and which was based on George Yule's reintroduction of pragmatic concepts, was developed and used for this specific study. Ultimately, the pragmatic language of the participants of the study, as evident through the findings, was characterized by five major themes: Reference and Inference, Logical Entailment, Politeness and Social Understanding, Discourse Comprehension, and Relationship with General Meaning. The themes indicated a variety in pragmatic skills and capabilities within the sample, and showed that autistic individuals exhibit diverse pragmatic profiles, challenging the notion of a uniform pragmatic ability across the spectrum.

Keywords: *Autism Spectrum Disorder, High-Functioning Autism, Language Ability, Pragmatic Assessment, Social Language.*

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Chapter One

Introduction

1 CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Overview

This chapter introduces the topic of pragmatic language abilities in autism spectrum disorder. A brief, informational background on pragmatic failure in autism and pragmatic competence assessment, is presented. The research problem is identified, the research aims, objectives, and questions are set forth, then, the significance of the study is highlighted. Key concepts and detailed definitions can be found following the significance of the study section. Finally, an outline of the entire study is provided, and the chapter concludes with a summary.

1.2 Background

Language studies in the field of Autism are typically reliant on the use of several evaluation methods and the results which they produce. The process of obtaining tangible solid numbers through scoring systems and numerical data analysis makes up the foundation of Autism research. When investigating more nuanced and sensitive areas of ability in relation to autism, such as pragmatic language, detail-sensitive procedures are required to encompass the full range of experiences of autistic people with verbal communication.

1.2.1 Pragmatic Failure in ASD

Language difficulties are a central symptom of autism, often manifesting as issues with social communication (DSM-5, 2013). Research shows that these difficulties are largely due to pragmatic impairments, especially in high-functioning individuals with ASD (Ambridge, B., Bidgood, A., & Thomas, K., 2020). Pragmatic failures in ASD can affect narrative comprehension, inference skills, and contextual awareness, leading to disjointed communication and challenges in maintaining coherent conversations (Colle, L., et al., 2007; Deliens, G., 2018). Additionally, difficulties with turn-taking, interpreting speech acts, and social deixis often result in misunderstandings and social awkwardness (Attwood, T., 2007; Yule, G., 1996).

1.2.2 The Effects of Pragmatic Failure in ASD

Pragmatic failures in ASD can be misinterpreted as social uncooperativeness, further isolating individuals from social interactions (Attwood, T., 2007; Balestro, J., 2017). This social isolation impacts not only personal relationships but also academic performance. Pragmatic competence is crucial for literacy and reading comprehension, areas where individuals with ASD often score lower compared to their neurotypical peers (Holloway, R., et al., 2013; Peristeri, E., et al., 2024). These challenges can hinder academic and professional success, despite strong grammatical skills (Thagard, L., et al., 2011).

1.2.3 Pragmatic Competence Assessment: An In-Depth Approach

In 1982, Prutting developed a protocol for assessing pragmatic aspects of language, which became highly influential (Sacco, K., et al., 2008). Following this, various protocols and assessment tools emerged, though a standardized model was not established until the Test of Pragmatic Language (TOPL) in 1992 (Prutting, C., & Kirchner, D., 1987). Subsequent tests, such as Bishop's Children's Communication Checklist (1998) and Gilliam and Miller's Pragmatic Language Skills Inventory (2006), have focused on specific pragmatic skills. While these tools are thorough, an all-encompassing assessment for initial evaluations in educational or pre-clinical settings could be valuable. Most current research uses quantitative methods, but qualitative approaches may offer deeper insights, particularly for specific populations like individuals with ASD (Bachman, L., 1998; Denzin, N., 2008; Ghafar, Z., 2023).

1.3 Research Problem

The pragmatic abilities of autistic individuals of varying age groups, backgrounds, and degrees of disability, have been investigated in different contexts, using different methods. From low-functioning to high-functioning individuals, children to adults; the autistic population has shown a uniform deficit in pragmatic competence (Hughes. O et al, 1988; Young. C et al 2005; Lam. G & Yeung. S, 2011; Volden. J & Phillips. L, 2010). The resulting effects of the lack have been explored as well, and found to have been at times detrimental to the ASD person's quality and nature of social and professional life (Cummings. L 2011; Whitehouse. A et al; 2009).

The assessment tools employed in the research of pragmatic skills in autism equally serve and function as aid in the full clinical diagnostic process of ASD; offering accuracy of symptom

observation (Dolata. J et al, 2022). The commonly utilized pragmatic assessment tests (TOPL-2, CCC-2, PLSI, TASIT, and CAPs) are thorough in nature, with a limited focus on specific pragmatic abilities; selected for evaluation in accordance with specific pragmatic concepts. In other words, the actual possible full range of pragmatic impairments in ASD may not be encapsulated in those tests (Volden. J & Phillips. L, 2010; Adams. C, 2008). A more broad and widely-inclusive understanding of the language difficulties in the ASD individuals may require the consideration of less commonly evaluated areas of pragmatic competence; which calls for different approaches (Volden. J & Phillips. L, Adams. C, 2002). For better - and equal- chances to obtain official diagnoses and assisting interventions for people with ASD, appropriate language assessment tools must be available to better identify the linguistic deficits in the individuals, including -and especially- in early pre-clinical contexts.

Additionally, the recurrent resort to the quantitative research method in previous pragmatic competence research in autism, although favoring and aiming towards objectivity and generalizability of findings, may overlook the potential advantages of specific-sample data and the in-depth observation of it, in a field of research where the individual experience is a valuable source of information (Denzin. N, 2008; Cridland. E et al, 2015; Schalkwyk. G & Dewinter. J, 2020). A magnified perspective on the autistic experience with pragmatic language deficits and social difficulties is a serviceable addition to the existing enlarging body of research in this particular area.

1.4 Aims and Objectives

The current study is an investigation of the pragmatic abilities of seven autistic Algerian teenagers, aged 13-18, from Ahmed Bouguerra middle school. This research aims to explore the characteristics of the participants' pragmatic profiles, using an assessment tool which was developed for employment in this specific study: a pragmatic competence test designed based on the fundamental *Reference and Inference*, *Presupposition and Entailment*, *Politeness and Interaction*, and *Discourse and Culture* concepts of pragmatics. The study will simultaneously be evaluating the functionality of said tool.

For the achievement of the mentioned aims, the following objectives are set forth:

1. Analyzing the individual pragmatic profiles of the ASD participants through their performance on the pragmatic test.

2. Identifying themes and patterns in the ASD participants' pragmatic understanding and use of language.
3. Discussing the implications of the results and the adequacy of the pragmatic test designed for this study.

1.5 Research Questions

This study will look into the pragmatic abilities of Algerian autistic teenagers, using a pragmatic evaluation test developed especially for the current purpose. The following research questions are expected to be tackled:

1. What are the pragmatic abilities of Algerian autistic teenagers?
2. Do the pragmatic profiles of Algerian autistic teenagers show unique individual patterns?
3. What do the pragmatic profiles of the Algerian autistic teenagers imply about the methodology used to achieve them?

1.6 Significance of the Study

The importance of the current research, firstly, directly relates to the limited studies on pragmatic competence in ASD; where an in-depth, wide-ranging approach is applied. The pragmatic test created as an evaluation instrument for this study dedicates attention to often overlooked areas of pragmatic ability. The mixed-method research method works hand in hand with the nature of the extracted data provided by the test; allowing for extensive results, as well. Additionally, the substantial lack -or rather absence- of academic works tackling the topic of pragmatic language abilities in ASD in Algeria specifically, calls for more dedicated efforts towards the investigation of this area of research with the consideration of cultural context. This study sheds light on the individual pragmatic profiles of autistic teenagers from Oran, Algeria, providing a new, in-depth perspective to the current global and local body of research in language and autism. The findings of this study are hoped to contribute to the goals of: raising autism awareness in Algerian educational institutions and society in general, the development of pre-clinical ASD language evaluation instruments to be used in the early process of diagnosis, and the adoption of more qualitative frameworks in autism research.

1.7 Definitions of Key Concepts

Autism Spectrum Disorder

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a neurodevelopmental condition marked by persistent deficits in social communication and restricted, repetitive patterns of behavior and interest (American Psychological Association, 2023). The "Spectrum" in ASD denotes the range of symptom severity, categorized into three levels as outlined in the DSM-5. Individuals may vary in their need for support, from minimal (high-functioning) to significant interventions (low-functioning) (Rudy, L. 2024). Although experiences differ, social communication challenges are a core aspect for most individuals with ASD.

Pragmatic Competence

Pragmatics studies meaning in context, focusing on the relationship between language, the user, and the situation (Yule, G. 1996). Pragmatic competence refers to the ability to use this knowledge to communicate effectively and appropriately. This involves understanding and employing various pragmatic concepts like Reference, Inference, Politeness, and Discourse. These concepts form the foundation of pragmatic skills, essential for the coherent and contextually appropriate use of language (Thomas, 1983; Leech, 1983).

1.8 Structure of the Study

This thesis contains five chapters:

Chapter One lays the foundational knowledge and background of the topic of pragmatic abilities in ASD; introducing key concepts and findings in autism and pragmatics. The research problem, aims and objectives, questions and significance of the study, are also set forth.

Chapter Two is a run-through of the existing literature on pragmatic competence in ASD that shaped the current study and its research questions. The relevant pieces of literature are reviewed, and their findings are directly related to the rudimentary components of this study.

Chapter Three is an outline of the study's employed methodology, which centers around a mixed-method approach. The design of the research is detailed; describing the assessment tool

created for the study, along with the participants and the process of selecting them, the limitations of that process, the data collection techniques and analysis strategies, and, finally, the researcher stance.

Chapter Four Chapter Four presents the results of the study alongside a discussion of the main findings. The initial themes discovered through the detailed process of data analysis are outlined, followed by a deeper examination of how these findings relate to previous research and theories in the field. The chapter also explores the potential implications of the results, offering direct answers to the research questions concerning the pragmatic abilities of autistic Algerian teenagers.

Chapter Five lays down the final conclusions of the study, brushing on what it contributes to language and autism research and making relevant suggestions for further improvements and future research.

1.9 Summary

In this chapter, the background of pragmatic language competence assessment in ASD was briefly discussed. The research problem was identified, and; through it, the aims, objectives, and questions of the study; which center around the pragmatic abilities of autistic teenagers from Oran, Algeria, were highlighted. Finally, the outline of the study is laid out, describing the contents of each chapter, followed by a terms and definitions section to better explain the key concepts and terminology that frequently appear in the study.

The following chapter contains the literature review about pragmatic competence assessment and research in ASD; featuring key and relevant findings in the area, as well as the studies on which the foundation for the current study was laid.

Chapter Two

Literature Review

2 CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Overview:

Chapter Two covers the literature on Pragmatic Language Assessment in ASD. This chapter details the previous most relevant existing works in the field, introduces the major concepts and significant studies, and places the current work in the map of similar research by presenting the conceptual framework for this study and highlighting the gap in literature which this study aims to fit into.

2.2 Pragmatic Language Ability in ASD

Autism is characterized by social and linguistic deficits which can impair the individual's ability to make successful interactions within their community. The linguistic deficits in particular are attributed to, or packaged as, a lack in pragmatic ability. This section details the prominent defining pieces of knowledge which have been obtained on autism.

2.2.1 Social Deficits in ASD

One of the primary criteria for recognizing and diagnosing ASD is an impairment or difficulty with social functioning. The earliest mentions of social impairments in ASD date back to 1943 and 1956; when Leo Kanner and Leon Eisenberg provided detailed observation of children with autism. These observations relied heavily on the extensive profiles and histories of the children. The socially centered observations entailed different instances and types of social impairments; including inattention to people and detachment from them, preference for solitude and focus on inner world, unawareness of the feelings of others, and an odd use of language (Baron-Cohen, S, 1988). A simple example of intact social functioning ability would be the capability to direct attention towards another person, maintain it appropriately, and respond accordingly using the information gathered from that engagement. In autism, there is a lack of interest in the conversing subject, therefore a difficulty to respond to what is being received.

Several studies followed throughout the years to explore this central defining characteristic of autism, each with a specific focus on a facet of social ability in ASD. Dewey and Evard (1974), and Newson, Dawson and Evard (1984), discovered that the unusual social characteristics of autism were not limited to children, but appeared even in autistic teenagers and adults; implying

the permanence of the condition. Later on, individuals with autism were discovered to not entirely avoid social interaction, nor fail to display interest, affection, or attention, but rather display them in a 'deviant' and unusual manner. Autistic individuals have shown a tendency to be more prone to engage in social behavior when the conditions of familiarity and routine are present; interacting within a safety structure (Lord, 1984, 1993). In 1990, Lord found that autistic teenagers and children have difficulties with attention-demanding, long, reciprocal social interactions with their peers; especially when spontaneous understanding is required.

The social deficit in autism was linked and even attributed to the serious cognitive deficit of Theory of Mind, which is defined as the individual's ability to attribute mental states to others, or make assumptions about their emotions, beliefs and knowledge (Tager-Flusberg. H, 1999); in autistic individuals (Baron-Cohen; Leslie and Frith, 1985, Harris and Muncer, 1988). Furthermore, the obvious link between social interaction and communication ties the social deficits and difficulty with language in autism together (Tager-Flusberg. H, 1999).

2.2.2 Communication and Language Deficits in ASD

Another hallmark for autistic behavior is the difficulty with language use and understanding. Individuals with autism show a unique and atypical relationship with language both in their comprehension and employment of it, which to typical standards is considered a deficit. Language to the autistic person serves very few purposes, and its functions are limited to things such as sharing information, seeking attention, clarifying personal intentions, or expressing mental states (Tager-Flusberg, 1992, 1993, 1997). In 1978, Ball noted that autistic children display a lack of awareness of social conversational rules and customs, such as turn-taking and reciprocity, and a difficulty to adhere to them; instead following their own pattern of communication. In 1994, Lee, Hobson and Chiat added to the notion that autistic children struggle with conversation and especially the relationship between the speaker and the listener; specifically in self-and-other distinction. In 1991, Anderson found that children with autism also struggle with the linearity and consistency of conversation, often following a divergent trail of transition between topics or points, making their contributions to the exchange appear irrelevant.

Other linguistic deficits in autism include the literal interpretation of language (Happé, 1993; Sperber & Wilson, 1986), where the intended meaning which is embedded in an utterance is missed by the autistic individual. This deficit was observed across autistic people of different

ages and levels of autism. Issues with narrative were observed in this population as well; where autistic children were seen to produce retellings of events, or narratives, characterized in misinterpretation of events, focus on secondary or relevant details, and poorly connected descriptions (Bruner & Feldman, 1993; Loveland & Tunali, 1993).

2.2.3 Pragmatic Deficits in ASD

All of the characteristics described above are essentially considered, and described as, pragmatic; especially in correlation with the backing evidence that they are related to Theory of Mind (Bruner & Feldman, 1993; Loveland & Tunali, 1993). Pragmatic ability, according to Jafari. P (2019) “comprises one of the underlying components of social communication that can be defined as a set of abilities used for the proper utilization and interpretation of language in different communicative situations.”, so it is fundamentally dependent on one’s capacity for social understanding and reciprocation, thus Theory of Mind ability (Locke, 1993; Sperber & Wilson, 1986).

2.2.3.1 Pragmatic Ability

Pragmatic ability serves as an active translator for language from the surface utterance a speaker uses to deliver an idea, to the inside meaning, which lies underneath, that they intend to deliver. It is the set of skills and unspoken rules of communication that a person relies on to understand language, or use it appropriately in different contexts. A competence in pragmatic ability not only facilitates social interactions significantly, but also allows the individual to express themselves freely, understand other people better, make the most sense of written materials, and be adaptable. In his 1996 book, George Yule redefined and reintroduced a variety of well-established pragmatic concepts, grouped by their in-real-life function in social interaction. Each concept represented a component of pragmatic ability and what it entails, and was explained through detailed examples of its use. Pragmatic Competence is achieved through the awareness of said concepts and the proper use of them. The following figure exhibits the concepts as introduced in the book.

Figure 2.1: Graph of the major pragmatic concepts

2.2.3.2 The Pragmatic Concepts

According to Yule, pragmatic ability requires an awareness of the pragmatic concepts most employed in social communication, the ability to recognize them, and the correct application of them. In his book, Yule presents eight major concepts, or, more specifically, the general pragmatic areas of ability which entail other minor concepts:

1. *Deixis and Distance*: Deixis refers to the act of pointing by using any linguistic form. The linguistic form is then called a ‘deictic expression’ or ‘indexicals’. The indexicals include ‘person deixis’ to indicate people, ‘spatial deixis’ to indicate location, and ‘temporal deixis’ to indicate time. Deixis refers to the context of the speaker, either using ‘near speaker’ (proximal terms) or ‘away from speaker’ (distal terms) of deictic expressions. The speaker’s location, so called ‘deictic center’, is identified by the proximal terms (Rahmah. F et al, 2016). For instance, in the sentence 'I will meet you here tomorrow,' 'I' is a personal deictic expression referring to the speaker, 'here' indicates the proximal location of the speaker, and 'tomorrow' is a temporal deictic expression pointing to the time relative to the speaker's current moment. In contrast, 'they will meet us there next

week' uses 'they' for the people referred to, 'there' for a location away from the speaker, and 'next week' for a future time not immediate to the speaker.

2. *Reference and Inference*: Reference is an act in which a speaker, or writer, uses linguistic forms to enable a listener, or reader, to identify something. It is directly tied to the speaker's goals (for example, to identify something) and the speaker's beliefs (i.e. can the listener be expected to know that particular something?) in the use of language. Inference, on the other hand, is simply the interpretation of the speaker's intended meaning (Yule. G, 1996). For example, in the sentence 'She left her keys on the table,' 'her keys' is a reference that assumes the listener knows which keys are being talked about. If the speaker and listener had previously discussed a specific set of keys, the listener uses inference to understand that 'her keys' refers to that particular set. In contrast, if the speaker had never mentioned the keys before, the listener might need more context to make the same inference.
3. *Presupposition and Entailment*: A presupposition is something assumed to be true in a sentence which asserts other information (Hudson, 2000). Entailment, then, refers to a relation between a pair of sentences such that the truth of the second sentence necessarily follows from the truth of the first (Crystal, 1998), e.g. 'I have caught the flu' logically also entails 'I am ill'. The assertion of the first statement requires the assertion of the second. For instance, in the sentence 'John stopped smoking,' the presupposition is that John used to smoke. The sentence itself asserts that John has ceased smoking, but it presupposes the prior fact of his smoking habit. In terms of entailment, the statement 'John is no longer a smoker' necessarily follows from 'John stopped smoking,' as the truth of the first sentence ensures the truth of the second.
4. *Cooperation and Implicature*: Yule (1996) explained that "The sense of cooperation is simply one in which people having a conversation are not normally assumed to be trying to confuse, trick or withhold relevant information from each other". Thus, cooperation concerns a basic assumption in conversation that each participant will attempt to contribute appropriately, at the required time, to the current exchange of talk. An implicature is an additional conveyed meaning, or a message which communicates something other than simply what the uttered words mean. For example, if person A says,

'Can you pass the salt?' and person B responds, 'The salt is on the table,' the implicature is that person B is not just stating the location but subtly indicating that passing the salt is expected. Cooperation in this context means that person B is providing a relevant and helpful response, even though it doesn't directly answer the request but implies the expected action.

5. *Speech Acts and Events*: According to Yule, “Actions performed via utterances are generally called speech acts and, in English, are commonly given more specific labels, such as apology, complaint, compliment, invitation, promise or request”. A speech situation is the context of language use such as ceremonies, fights, classrooms, parties, etc. it is associated with speech but it is not governed by rules of speaking; however, a speech event is governed by rules of speaking and it takes place within a speech situation. A speech situation is a setting where language is used, such as an educational setting, a celebration or an argument. Although it is related to speech, it is not controlled by conversational conventions; on the other hand, a speech event is subject to conversational conventions and occurs within a speech situation. For example, at a wedding ceremony (a speech situation), a speech act might be the officiant’s utterance of 'I now pronounce you husband and wife,' which performs the action of marrying the couple. Within this speech situation, the speech event would be the specific act of pronouncing the couple married, governed by the rules and conventions of wedding ceremonies and formal language.
6. *Politeness and Interaction*: Politeness is a reserve of social skills whose main aim is to make sure all parties, including oneself, in a social interaction feel affirmed and considered (William, 1997). Yule (1996) also describes it as “the means employed to show awareness of another person's face”. Face, as Brown and Levinson’s (1978) define it, is “the public self-image that every member wants for himself”. For instance, when requesting a favor, saying 'Could you please pass the salt?' instead of 'Pass the salt' demonstrates politeness by showing consideration for the other person's face. The politeness strategy here helps maintain a positive social interaction and respects the other person's public self-image, or 'face,' by making the request more indirect and respectful.

7. *Discourse and Culture*: according to Gee (2016), discourse refers to a group of people's shared ways of communication, including how they express their thoughts, emotions, beliefs and morals through language; meaning that each distinct group of people have their own distinct discourse characteristics which imply their social belonging and identity. Culture is commonly known as the shared values and attitudes in a community, and, in relation to discourse, is the social background which sets the rules for the use of language within the community (Abu Karim. M, 2024). For instance, in a corporate environment, the discourse might include formal language and specific jargon related to business practices, reflecting a culture of professionalism and hierarchy. In contrast, a group of friends might use informal language and slang, which reflects a culture of casual and personal interaction. These different discourses illustrate how language use is shaped by and reinforces the cultural norms of each group.

8. *Conversation and Preference Structure*: Conversation Structure refers to the organized pattern of interactions in conversations, including turn-taking, adjacency pairs (question-answer sequences, for example), and repair mechanisms to maintain clarity. Preference Structure describes the socially expected patterns of responses, where some responses (like accepting an invitation) are preferred, and align with conversational norms, while others (like declining) are dispreferred and often require additional explanation or mitigation (Yule. G, 1996). For example, in a conversation where one person says, 'Would you like to join us for dinner?' The preferred response is 'Yes, I'd love to,' which aligns with social norms of acceptance. A dispreferred response might be 'No, I can't make it,' which could require additional explanation or a polite excuse to soften the impact and maintain conversational harmony.

2.3 Prior Studies

Several studies tested people for pragmatic competence as a whole through the consideration of several pragmatic elements of capacity. The tools employed for the evaluation in said studies varied depending on the approaches of the researchers. Each of the studies targeted different objectives, but fell under the general aim of language assessment as a whole.

Most recently, Eline Aaland et al, (2024), used two translated assessment instruments: the Pragma test, and the Children's Communication Checklist-2, to test the pragmatic abilities of Norwegian children. Ana Miranda et al, (2023), utilized several tools of assessment in a longitudinal study, including a standardized pragmatic language test (CCC-2), a sub-scale of the SSBS, the VABS-II, and the SDQ questionnaire, to arrive at the social outcomes of pragmatic language deficit in children with ASD. In 2023, Fadhlur Rahman et al developed an online pragmatic assessment test to evaluate 52 EFL learners for pragmatic competence, and investigated possible background reasons for the results (notably exposure to second language). The studies showed that the used assessment tools were reliable in educational and language learning contexts. Other studies, on the other hand, were wholly dedicated to testing specific abilities separately. In 1999, Sonia Yoshitake-Strain used the multi-test framework developed by Hudson, Detmer, and Brown, to measure the Deixis and Distance and Speech Acts ability of native Japanese learners (Hudson et al., 1992, 1995). In 2012, Elly Ifantidou and Angeliki Tzanne developed a written Discourse focused assessment tool to test the writing abilities of L2 students. In 2016, Giorgio Arcara and Valentina Bambini used the six-task test: *Assessment of Pragmatic Abilities and Cognitive Substrates* assessment, to test Discourse and non-literal language abilities of 119 participants. The studies showed that pragmatic competence is a multi-faceted ability with interlinked skills, and that assessing it necessitates an all-encompassing, multi-level process of testing. The studies also supported the supposition that pragmatic assessment tools which test multiple abilities are a much more reliable source of data for when it comes to accurate pragmatic evaluation.

In the field of autism, more specifically, a solid body of research contains investigations of certain pragmatic abilities with and without the use of a pragmatic assessment test as the main research tool of the study. Loukusa et al (2007), compared the inference abilities of two groups of high-functioning autistic children with different ages, revealing a tendency in the younger participants to have more difficulties with context. Pijnacker et al (2009), tested the Implicature ability of high-functioning adults with ASD, and found that they performed poorly compared to a control group. Nobury and Bishop (2002), found high-functioning individuals with autism to perform poorly when it came to narrative comprehension and non-literal language in comparison to their typically developing peers. Kerbel & Grunwell, 1998, discovered that children with ASD had difficulties with understanding idioms. Heavy et al (2000) created an instrument of linguistic

assessment to test high-functioning autistic individuals for discourse comprehension and social understanding, arriving at the finding that the study's subjects had difficulties with telling the mental states and intentions of others (Loukusa. S; Moilanen. B, 2009). The range of pragmatic concepts covered in the existing literature is broad, encompassing several pragmatic skills and labeling them explicitly as pragmatic.

2.4 Pragmatic Assessment in Autism

In both clinical diagnosis processes and academic research for ASD, standardized pragmatic tests have consistently proven to be a valuable tool for the evaluation of social-linguistic skills by measures of convenience and reliability. Numerous studies relied primarily on one or more pragmatic language assessment tests to obtain the data that is needed to form a picture on the tested population's profile of ability. Although there exists multiple standardized pragmatic tests, only some of them hold the spot of the typically and mostly used. Figure 2.2 exhibits well-known pragmatic tests, organized by relative popularity, use, and mentions in autism research.

Figure 2.2: Pragmatic assessment tests

1. *The Children's Communication Checklist (Second Edition)*: First published in 1998, the CCC was developed by D.V.M Bishop, then improved in 2003, to identify language impairments in children, evaluate their pragmatic abilities, and recognize possible symptoms of ASD to be able to direct the child for further clinical investigation. The test follows a scoring system. It is meant to be filled out by an adult who is in consistent proximity with the child being tested, then sent for interpretation by a professional. Consisting of 70 multiple choice items, and ten scales of measure which evaluate different strengths and weaknesses in the child's use of language, the H scale is the one which covers pragmatic aspects specifically (Bishop, 2003). The test has been used in multiple studies to evaluate the pragmatic skills of individuals with autism, differentiate between them and individuals who have language-affecting conditions, and test the usability and validity of the test itself. Jill K. Dolata et al (2022) used the CCC-2 to check if its scoring system will be able to display a distinction between 174 children; ASD participants, controls, and a population with a different neurodevelopmental condition. The test was able to provide the distinction between the three different groups, confirming its usability. More recently, Inmaculada Baixauli-Fortea et al (2023) investigated the characteristics of pragmatic ability in ASD children to create a descriptive profile of their language skills using the CCC-2. The autistic sample were compared to typically-developing controls, and performed significantly lower in contrast to them.
2. *The Test of Pragmatic Language (Second Edition)*: Initially introduced in 1992, the Test of Pragmatic Language was developed, for children and teenagers, by Diana Phelps-Terasaki and Trisha Phelps-Gunn, and further improved in 2007. The test's aim is to recognize pragmatic deficits, measure the difficulties and capacities which characterize one's communication, and track their improvement in therapy, testing specifically six core dimensions of pragmatic language: Context, audience, topic, speech-acts, visual cues and abstractions. For its employment, the test requires both the examinee, and an examiner for guidance, assistance through the process, and scoring the examinee's responses. The examiner introduces an item from a picture book, and the examinee is expected to provide an accurate description (*Child Language Disorders Fall 2017*). In one study, Joanne Volden and Linda Phillips (2010) tested the pragmatic abilities of 16

autistic children and 16 controls by providing them with the TOPL, and their parents with the CCC-2. The aim was to make a comparison between the two tests' abilities to distinguish autistic individuals better by highlighting their pragmatic deficits. The TOPL was accurate in not identifying any of the controls as pragmatically impaired, but only identified 9 out of the 16 autistic participants as having pragmatic difficulties. In 2019, Zohre Arani Kashani used a Persian version of the test with the aim to check for the validity of its standardization. The study evaluated 15 participants, and with an impact factor of 4.8, the translated version of the test proved to be reliable for assessment in more professional settings.

3. *The Comprehensive Assessment of Spoken Language*: Created by Elizabeth Carrow-Woolfolk to identify language deficits, the Comprehensive Assessment of Spoken Language evaluates spoken language in fifteen tests, covering four categories: Lexical/Semantic, Syntactic, Supralinguistic and Pragmatic. The test is available for children, teenagers, and adults all alike (Pearson, 2024). The testing process is meant to be administered only by those in the fields relating to language, psychology, or education. In one recent study, Matthew Phillips (2023) wanted to check for pragmatic ability differences between male and female autistic children. The CASL was used in this study to provide scores for analysis, along with other assessment instruments. Upon thorough comparison, girls with ASD exhibited better social skills and higher pragmatic ability than boys with ASD.

4. *The Social Language Development Test*: The SLDT, popular for its use in identifying ASD, was developed by Linda Bowers, Rosemary Huisingh, and Carolyn M. LoGiudice. The first version of the test, Elementary, was developed in 2008, followed by the Adolescent version in 2008, and updated in 2016. The test is pragmatics-centered in the way it focuses on social linguistic skills, assessing Interaction, Inference, Politeness, and the ability to understand context and accurately interpret language, and it is made up of subtests consisting of question-answering tasks, interpretations of photographed scenes, and verbal explanations. The test is meant to be administered and scored by a professional, following specific guidelines which are included with it (Mind Resources, 2024). In one study, Miranda J Clark (2012), evaluated the social skills of adolescents

with high-functioning autism, Asperger's syndrome, and neurotypical development. The study relied on the standard scores of the Adolescent version of the test as the primary source of data. The test highlighted a social impairment in the ASD groups, which did not perform as well as the neurotypical group, although Asperger's adolescents were shown to perform better than the high-functioning autistic adolescents. In another study, however, Jennifer C. Zeberlein (2014) discovered that the SLDT had limited capacity for identifying social impairments. The study included four participant groups: ASD children, Asperger's children, ADHD children, and typically-developing controls, and used both the SLDT and the CCC-2 for contrast.

5. *The Pragmatic Language Skills Inventory*: Published by Gilliam & Miller in 2006, the Pragmatic Language Skills Inventory is a norm-referenced evaluation instrument designed to measure the pragmatic abilities of children from five to ten years old. Distinctively, the 45-item test was designed on the basis of well-known pragmatic theories and concepts, and was primarily targeted towards teachers and other workers of educational settings, serving as a tool of early intervention (Valdespino, J. 2013). A study by Gulce Alev et al (2014), used a translated Turkish version of the PLSI to check for pragmatic deficits, indicative of autism and intellectual disabilities, in a notably large sample (1000+). The test proved to be reliable even when translated to fit a different cultural context. In 2014, Diken. Ö, used the PLSI along with an autism rating scale to assess the pragmatic abilities of 86 children with developmental disabilities, including autism, in Turkey. The autistic children outperformed the children with developmental disabilities in the PLSI test, but still showed very deficient pragmatic ability.

2.5 Conceptual Framework and Research Gap

The current-day body of available literature on pragmatic language assessment in ASD is highlighted by recurring themes and characteristics which link each study to another. The current study is based on the investigation of said recurring themes and links which formed its conceptual framework. The following figure highlights the major linked elements which could be consistently found throughout the literature.

Figure 2.3: The conceptual framework

The conceptual framework of this current study is mapped out and put-together by the researcher. This framework lays the foundation of the study by positioning it within the map of similar studies, and guiding the research design and the methodology of it. The model summarizes the combination of the most prominent characteristics and elements in the literature. The elements are labeled as follows:

1. *Focus of the Study:* In the Pragmatic Assessment in ASD studies reviewed in this chapter, the main areas of focus which determine the studies' aims, objectives, and questions were consistent in occurrence. First, the investigation of pragmatic ability in general, as in the sum of the participants' social-linguistic capacity elements, without the reliance on individual pragmatic concepts or elements . Alternatively, a few certain areas of pragmatic ability, as in specific skills within the larger pragmatic areas of ability (or 'concepts' as referred to in this study), were the considered centerpiece of other studies. These approaches proved reliable in detecting pragmatic deficits and identifying individuals with ASD amongst other participants, although they fell short as an accurate,

ASD specific, all-encompassing pre-clinical assessment tool with the ability to distinguish between children with ASD and other neurodevelopmental conditions.

According to Clara-Andres Roqueta et al (2024) “pragmatic skills are often only partially assessed because the existing instruments usually focus on specific aspects of pragmatics and are not always adapted to children with communication difficulties.”

In the current study, the aim of the assessment is the curation of an extensive pragmatic profile measured by major pragmatic concepts, taking into consideration both the general degree of pragmatic ability of the participant, as well as the specific areas of difficulty that they may especially characterize their individual profile.

2. *Methodology of The Study:* Notably, the majority of studies on pragmatic assessment in ASD follow a quantitative methodological approach, relying on numerical data and descriptive or inferential statistics. The validity of these studies is also closely tied to the sample size and the accuracy of the data. These studies show an interest in generalizable findings which can contribute to the objective body of knowledge on pragmatic ability in ASD, rather than the nuanced experiences of the participants. The current study takes on a qualitative approach by using an assessment test not for the purpose of obtaining general scores of pragmatic ability, but to gather qualitative data for analysis. The analysis aims to uncover detailed characteristics of the participants’ pragmatic profiles. Moreover, the sample size is narrowed to achieve maximum accuracy.
3. *Data Collection Method of the Study:* Standardized pragmatic language assessment tests are the most commonly resorted-to tool of data collection in the pragmatic ability in ASD studies, in some cases coupled with one another or with additional research instruments developed by the researchers or in previous studies. These data collection tools are typically used to gather statistical or numerical data because of the scoring systems attached to them, categorizing the participants’ answers on a scale of correctness. In the current study, the utilized assessment test does not grade the participants, but simply acts as a collection tool to obtain written data that is priorly categorized according to the test’s design.

2.5.1 The Research Gap

Despite the considerable body of research investigating the pragmatic language deficits in individuals with ASD, with a focus on social communication and the Theory of Mind specifically, a number of gaps remain unappraised in the literature. Most existing studies centered around specific pragmatic abilities, or used standardized assessment tests to measure pragmatic competence. However, these studies do not consider or delve into the full range of pragmatic concepts needed for a comprehensive understanding of pragmatic language deficits in ASD.

Firstly, many studies relied on well-established tests like the CCC-2 or the TOPL to evaluate pragmatic abilities. These tools, while valuable and commonly employed in clinical settings, are still limited in their scope, often focusing on certain aspects of pragmatic language such as context, topic management, or speech acts. This leaves a considerable gap in the assessment of other fundamental and important pragmatic skills, such as inference, deixis, entailment, politeness, and discourse.

Furthermore, there is a lack of studies that integrate multiple pragmatic concepts into a single assessment framework. Most research either focuses on one or two aspects of pragmatic ability or uses tools that assess pragmatic language as part of a broader language evaluation, without delving deeply into the nuances of each pragmatic skill. This fragmented approach limits the understanding of how different pragmatic abilities interact and contribute to the overall communication challenges faced by individuals with ASD.

Finally, while the majority of studies focused on autistic children, significantly less research was dedicated to teenagers or adults, overlooking potential changes in pragmatic competence as individuals with ASD age, especially during key developmental stages like adolescence when social communication and social performance demands increase. Additionally, there is a notable lack of research focusing on the pragmatic language abilities of high-functioning individuals with ASD in non-Western contexts, as most studies were conducted in Western countries, limiting the exploration of how cultural and linguistic differences may affect pragmatic language use and assessment in these individuals.

This study aims to address these gaps by developing a more comprehensive assessment tool of pragmatic language abilities in high-functioning autistic teenagers, by focusing on a broader range of pragmatic concepts. Additionally, this research seeks to contribute to a more nuanced understanding of pragmatic language deficits in ASD and provide valuable insights for both assessment and intervention strategies.

2.6 Summary

Chapter two provided a critical overview of the works in Pragmatic Assessment in ASD literature which this study was based on. Key studies in the field were introduced, as well as significant concepts, for the purpose of pinpointing where the current study is placed. The conceptual framework of the study is presented and the research gap is identified.

The next chapter outlines the methodology of the study, detailing the research design choices, explaining them, and justifying them in relation to the concepts discussed in chapter two. Chapter three also introduces the data collection instrument, which was designed for the study, and the data analysis method.

Chapter Three

Methodology

3 CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY

3.1 Overview:

The current chapter aims to present, outline and detail the research methodology which was applied in this study for the purpose of investigating the pragmatic abilities of Algerian autistic teenagers. This chapter frames and describes the research design; entailing the employed approach of the study, the research philosophy, type, and strategy; as well as the time horizon, sampling strategy, data collection method, and data analysis method; providing a wide review of the research process and its every step, and explaining the methodology choices. A summary of the presented steps and approaches concludes the chapter.

3.2 Research Design

Each design element in this study was set forth in relevance to the other, ensuring the interconnectedness and accuracy of the entire process. The research philosophy, type, and strategy are all in cohesiveness with the adopted approach, supported by the convenience of the time horizon and sampling strategy, and finally complemented by the adequate data collection and analysis methods. The following graph illustrates and summarizes the main facets of the current study's research design.

Figure 3.1: The Research Design

3.2.1 Research Approach

In this study, a mixed method research approach was adopted to investigate the pragmatic language abilities of seven Algerian autistic teenagers. According to Cresswell (2007), the qualitative approach is defined as “a means for exploring and understanding the meaning individuals or groups ascribe to a social or human problem”. The specific and in-depth nature of it offers a profounder and more socially-concerned perspective, and allows the researcher to reach results that are detailed and thorough. The quantitative approach is defined as “the processes of collecting, analyzing, interpreting, and writing the results of a study.” Paired with the reliability of the quantitative approach and the accuracy of numbers, which appear as frequencies in this study, the qualitative approach holds more validity, and the mixed method approach of this study serves its aims best; enabling the researcher to take a close look at the autistic individuals in particular, and their pragmatic relationship with language.

The mixed-method approach was used in this study for several reasons. First, pragmatic language ability is a very specific and nuanced proportion of general language ability; which must be attended to separately due to its complexity. Pragmatic language skills are linked to the pragmatic concepts which determine how people understand and create meaning in a social context, thus making those concepts important to consider. Second, the global autistic community is a vast and especially diverse one, with each autistic individual differing in needs, abilities and personal characteristics; making generalization difficult to achieve even with limited samples as in the current study; which specifically looks at seven Algerian teenagers with ASD. Finally, the resulting written data allows for better investigation and treatment of the material at hand, providing the researcher with not only a large body of information to work with, but also with the space to observe phenomena and make better deductions.

3.2.2 Research Philosophy

Interpretivism is the notion which states that knowledge is subjective and relative to real lived experiences. It takes into consideration the context of the research and its effects on the ultimate results (Blackwell. G, 2018). In this study, subjective interpretation was selected over objective measurements to better understand the unique experiences of Algerian autistic teenagers with pragmatic language, and gain insight on their perspective. The research data is mined for underlying meanings through the identification of patterns, followed by interpretation, and details like the participants' condition, environment, and level of autism, are taken into account. The taken philosophical stance aligns closely with the case-study research strategy and its intended objectives.

3.2.3 Research Type

It is a commonality for inductive reasoning to go hand-in-hand with qualitative research, and this study relies on a mixed-method approach. The inductive approach to research is defined as starting from observations from the data to end at conclusions or theories; meaning that unlike deductive research, the validity of a theory is not tested with the starting point being the theory itself, but the analysis of the data shapes the ultimate theory (Hecker. G; Kalpokas. N, 2024). In this study, detailed and specific observations were made about different occurrences in the participants' written answers to the pragmatic assessment test used to gather the data, and confirmatory numbers were presented, so that broader generalizations could be achieved from there.

Figure 3.2: The steps of the inductive method.

3.2.4 Research Strategy

A case study, according to Arya Priya (2020), is “A qualitative design in which the researcher explores in-depth a program, event, activity, process, or one or more individuals”. In a case study, the aim is to have a close perspective on the observed subject in its real-world context. The current research is a case study, where seven autistic teenagers from Oran, Algeria, aged from 13 to 18, are assessed for their pragmatic language skills in an educational setting. This particular strategy was a lucrative addition for this study, coupled with reliance on numbers for accuracy, because it offers a detailed look at the experiences of autistic people with pragmatic language use and understanding, and their unique individual characteristics of pragmatic ability.

3.2.4.1 Context of the the Study

The study was conducted in an educational environment, chosen for the aspect of familiarity for the participants. Considering the tendency to favor familiar and habitual experiences and environments in ASD (Jenkins. R, 2019); the setting was the middle school Ahmed Bouguerra where the selected participants attend, to ensure their comfort and ability to complete the assessment test. The participants were instructed on how to approach the written pragmatic

assessment test which was provided to them, and given no specific time limit to fill in their answers. If needed, help to read certain passages or understand questions was provided by the researcher who was present as the participants took the test.

3.2.5 Time Horizon

Considering that current study focuses on a group of a specific population, it adopts a cross-sectional study design. A cross-sectional design aims to observe and investigate the selected research participants at the same time; and the participants are simply chosen according to the criteria set for the study (Setia. M, 2016). In the current study, this design was primarily a natural outcome of the context of the study, and secondarily because it is not a longitudinal study, with no intention to observe the same participants through different points in time. The participants were gathered for the pragmatic assessment at the same time, and the data analysis process occurred after the data collection.

3.2.6 Sampling Strategy

A purposive sampling technique was seen to be the most suitable for the type of the current research, with the objective of making the best with the limited available resources. This technique, according to Cresswell & Plano Clark (2011) entails “Identifying and selecting individuals or groups of individuals that are especially knowledgeable about or experienced with a phenomenon of interest” (Palinkas. L et al, 2015). In the case of this study, the researcher specifically and intentionally sought out individuals who were formally and professionally diagnosed with ASD, and who fit into the age bracket of 13 to 18 years old. Figure 3.3 represents the selection criteria set and followed during the process of participant sampling.

Figure 3.3: The participant selection process

3.2.6.1 Demographic Data and Selection Process

As depicted in the figure above, the participants also had to be capable of finishing the assessment test comfortably without having significant issues with reading and writing. Although some of the low-functioning individuals, which were considered for the study, initially participated in the pragmatic assessment testing; their answers were ultimately eliminated as possible analyzable data, due to issues such as unintelligibility or lack of information within the answer sheets. The total number of test-takers was 11 before the selection step, and only 7 of them were considered as the participants to fit the criteria by the end of it.

Age, Gender and Educational level:

The table below details the ages, gender, and educational level of the participants. All of the participants do not exceed the brackets of teenagehood, and only one the seven participants is female. The participants are all from the same class, and have been classified together, as

explained by the school psychologist, because they share the same level of intellectual capacity. The latter had been determined by a testing procedure which was done in the school upon the registration of the students, as part of the middle school's protocols. With the confirmation that the participants all possess equal capacities to understand and complete the assessment test in this study, the selection process was precise in its considerations, and took into account any possibility of influential variables.

Participant	Age	Sex	Class
Abdelkader	18	Male	3M1
Oussama	17	Male	3M1
Farouk	15	Male	3M1
Ali	15	Male	3M1
Lahsen	15	Male	3M1
Walid	15	Male	3M1
Marwa	13	Female	3M1

Table 3.4: Sample information.

3.2.6.2 Ethical considerations

The researcher took into careful consideration any of the ethical issues that could arise in the line of research of the current nature, including sensitivity and respect to individuals and research sites (Creswell, 2012). Access to the research site, the middle school, was requested of its administration in advance and granted formally by the school psychologist after consideration of the request. Additionally, The seven participants, aged from 13 to 18 years old, were recruited by the very same school psychologist after looking through the institution's student files to select only the attendees confirmed and registered as having ASD and possessing the ability to read and write with ease. The informed consent to take part in the research was granted from both the participants themselves and their guardians after being informed of what the research and data collection procedure would entail by the researcher. Ultimately, the participants had no issue with taking the written pragmatic assessment test even when clearly informed that their

participation was entirely voluntary, and that they can choose to withdraw from the assessment test at any point during the study with no consequences. The participants' confidentiality was protected by not revealing their full identity; although their first names and ages were kept and mentioned for reference.

3.2.7 Data Collection Method

The data of this study was obtained through the distribution of a written pragmatic test amongst the attending participants, to acquire their answers. The answers were not only expected to contain the participants' responses to the tasks presented in the test, but also to display their own use of language as a secondary function. The participants agreed to stay after their regular scheduled classes to take the test, which was in the standardized Arabic language, in a quiet classroom with no external disturbances, and were in the presence of the researcher and school psychologist during the entirety of the process. The written pragmatic assessment test used to collect the data in this study was specifically made for it, and not adopted from any external source. The assessment test was based on several pragmatic concepts which make up pragmatic ability (Yule. G, 1996).

3.2.7.1 The Pragmatic Assessment Test

The pragmatic assessment tests utilized in this study served as the main data collection tool for it. The test was developed for the purpose of gathering written responses for analysis from the participants. It contained five tasks in total; each testing a specific pragmatic ability. Furthermore, the tasks were also initially based on said pragmatic abilities. Figure 3.4 details the test's tasks and the pragmatic concepts they were formed around.

Figure 3.5: The foundational pragmatic concepts and the tasks they shaped

As apparent in the graph above, the pragmatic concepts which served as the foundation for the assessment tasks were *Reference and Inference*, *Presupposition and Entailment*, *Politeness and Interaction*, and *Discourse and Culture*. This set of particular pragmatic concepts was selected by measure of significance amongst other pragmatic abilities, and frequency of use. The tasks were created accordingly to evaluate the participants ability at implementing the mentioned pragmatic concepts and using them in the correct manner. Each task corresponded to a concept, except for the last Critical Reading exercise; which was meant to test the general understanding of meaning.

3.2.7.2 Validity of Pragmatic Assessment Test

Prior to arriving at the final version of the pragmatic test which was used in the study, several drafts of its initial design were presented to a licensed psychologist to obtain important insights and make changes and corrections to render the test suitable for the autistic teenagers who were

going to take it. With constant reference to the source material which the test was based on (Yule. G, 1996), the design was polished and made usable for the study. The final version was approved by the same psychologist; who has extensive experience with autism and language disorders, as well as the researcher's academic supervisor; who is a Doctor in Linguistics.

3.2.8 Analysis Method

Thematic analysis is a qualitative research method for highlighting, investigating, engaging with and interpreting patterns of meaning in data (Clarke. V; Braun. V, 2015). This method is especially practical when the aim of the research is to uncover the meanings which lay in specific experiences, and tackle linguistic passages in an in-depth manner. Additionally, a frequency calculation aids in the broad visualization of the data patterns. The thematic analysis is further enhanced by the illustrative quality of numerical data. In this study, several steps were systematically followed to warrant the adequate functionality of the used methods.

3.2.8.1 Preparation of Data

Upon collecting the pragmatic assessment test sheets from the participants, an initial read-through was performed to determine which of the submitted sheets were going to be cut out for the more thorough data analysis procedure. Any answer sheets with completely unintelligible responses or handwriting, or mostly vacant spaces and skipped tasks, were not selected for the analysis. Only seven out of the eleven test sheets were chosen to be thematically analyzed; to ensure the accuracy and relevancy of the results. Moreover; the picked-out test sheets were then manually translated from Arabic to English by the researcher. The translation attempted to keep the answers as faithful to the original in structure and meaning as possible, and did not change, remove from, or add to the answers of the participants in any way.

3.2.8.2 Coding the Data

The pragmatic assessment test sheets of each one the seven participants were thoroughly read through and familiarized with to ensure full understanding of their contents, and the relationship between the posed questions and the answers provided by the students. The translated test sheets were imported into the free thematic analysis software: *MAXQDA Analytics Pro (2024)*, to start the coding process. An unpaid version of the software is available for access on the internet, along with user instructions. After several readings of the data, the codes with which to label and

organize the data were created by the researcher, directly into the program, to refer to the specific contents of the test sheets. The data was coded thoroughly, and the software was convenient in keeping track of each code, its instances, frequency, as well as the number of codes in each individual test sheet, for each participant. Table 3.5 is a list of all of the used codes and what they refer to.

Code	Significance
<i>Inference Success</i>	The participant displayed the ability to make correct inferences.
<i>Successful Recall of Reference</i>	The participant kept a previously mentioned reference in mind and took it into account to make an inference.
<i>Inference Failure</i>	The participant could not make an inference.
<i>Lacking Inference</i>	The participant made an incomplete and insufficient inference
<i>Logical Inconsistency</i>	The participant disregarded the chain of logic in the example.
<i>Entailment Failure</i>	The participant could not make a logical entailment.
<i>Logical Entailment</i>	The participant was successful at making an accurate logical entailment.
<i>Politeness Lack</i>	The participant failed to respond in a socially appropriate manner and be mindful of their language.
<i>Politeness Awareness</i>	The participant showed awareness of other people's states and emotions, and responded accordingly.
<i>No Face-Saving Act</i>	The participant failed to employ a face-saving act for themselves or the person in the example.
<i>Discourse Understood</i>	The participant was able to accurately understand the contents of a conversation.
<i>Discourse Misunderstood</i>	The participant was unaware of the implications and meaning of a conversation.
<i>Missed Meaning</i>	The participant had a general difficulty with meaning while reading a passage.
<i>Recognized Meaning</i>	The participant displayed a decent ability to understand written passages.
<i>Superficial Understanding</i>	The participant failed to access the deeper meaning of an uttering or passage.
<i>Irrelevant/Addition</i>	The participant strayed off of the focus of the current idea, or unnecessarily elaborated on it.
<i>Specific/ Literal</i>	The participant was misled by paying attention to

	a very specific detail in a passage, or taking the passage literally.
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Table 3.6: A list of codes and what they represent in the data.

3.2.8.3 Themes and Sub-themes

In thematic analysis, code patterns are meant to become evident in the data either through recurrence, similarities, or commonalities (Delve; Ho. L; &Limpaecher. A, 2022). Following the coding process in the current study, the previously coded data was grouped into major themes and sub-themes which summarize the significance of the codes’ patterns and instances. The themes and sub-themes were directly constructed from the codes by organizing the ones which fall under the same category, or represent the same pragmatic concept, together. Ultimately, five main themes and ten sub-themes were generated by the end of the process.

3.3 Summary

In this chapter, the methodology of the current study was introduced and explained. The research design choices, which were made by the researcher, were presented and justified to provide a well-rounded understanding of the research process. The chapter went over the research approach for this study, the research philosophy, the research type, the research strategy, as well as the used methods of data collection and analysis. The stages of the process were all listed and detailed, as well as supported by illustrations.

The next chapter displays the results of the data analysis, which were obtained through the implementation of the thematic analysis as mentioned in this chapter. Chapter four also provides the findings of the study by presenting the resulting themes and sub-themes of the data analysis. Thorough descriptions of the results are provided.

Chapter Four

Findings and Discussion

4 CHAPTER FOUR: FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Overview

In this chapter, the resulting findings of the data analysis; using the thematic analysis method and program-generated frequency graphs, are presented and described, as well as discussed and considered in relation to previous studies. The major themes discovered through the detailed examination of data from the pragmatic assessment test answers are demonstrated, along with the sub-themes they entail, and the frequencies generated by the data analysis software. This chapter is structured to present each theme individually, followed by its sub-themes.

4.2 Description of Key Findings

In the current mixed-method study, a thematic analysis was employed to explore the recurring themes in the answers to a pragmatic assessment test. Specifically, five themes emerged from the process of analyzing the originally written data; containing two sub-themes each. The themes and sub-themes encapsulate the different major facets of pragmatic ability in the autistic teenagers who were tested, having been drawn out from their own patterns of language use, as well as the individual answers to the questions presented in the pragmatic assessment test. These themes offer a perspective on the unique pragmatic profiles of Algerian teenagers with ASD, their shared characteristics, and their differences; providing answers to the previously introduced research questions. Figure 4.1 exhibits the themes.

Figure 4.1: The main themes.

The figure above presents the major themes which surfaced and have been made clear through the careful inspection of data using a thematic analysis. The themes represent the different areas of pragmatic ability considered for making a pragmatic assessment and, simultaneously, the characteristics of pragmatic ability in the Algerian autistic teenagers selected for this study. More evidently, the themes are the principal findings of the current study.

4.2.1 Descriptions of Themes and Sub-themes Extracted from Assessment Test Answers

A total of five themes was arrived-at by assessing the pragmatic language ability of seven participants, using a written pragmatic assessment test designed for this very study. The written answers of the participants were thematically analyzed, and from there, their patterns of language use and understanding; found in the written text itself, and their pragmatic abilities; found in the answers the written text aims to represent, appeared to create the main defined themes. Several sub-themes relating to the main themes emerged as well, each contributing to, and fitting in, the concept of the major theme it belongs under. Detailed descriptions of the pragmatic abilities of the seven Algerian autistic teenagers who participated in this study are going to be provided in this section, divided by theme. Graph 4.2 summarizes the found sub-themes under their respective main themes.

Figure 4.2: An outline of the themes and their respective sub-themes.

Theme 1: Reference and Inference

The ability to understand references and make inferences accordingly is an important factor of pragmatic competence, ensuring the capacity to follow narratives and arrive at the desired conclusions in a linear way. This theme was discovered through the very first task in the pragmatic assessment test: Reading Comprehension; which aimed to check the participants' ability to follow through plainly provided information in a written passage. The answers provided by the participants on the task highlighted the presence, or rather absence, as well, of this particular pragmatic concept in their use and understanding of language; with both a competence and a difficulty in proper reference and inference apparent in their responses. The theme occurred with all seven participants in different patterns; and its sub-themes occurred in identical frequencies. Figure 4.3 displays the frequency of Reference and Inference sub-themes.

Figure 4.3: A graph comparing the frequency of the Reference and Inference sub-themes.

Sub-theme 1.1: Inference Competence

In the first task of the pragmatic assessment test, the participants were expected to answer reading comprehension questions after reading through a small passage. The questions were direct and only required an accurate understanding of the passage to be answered correctly. Seven out of seven participants showed an ability to successfully recall references, and draw accurate and relevant inferences from the provided passage accordingly, in answering at least two of the six questions of the task.

To the question requesting the reason for postponing a competition; previously stated in the passage (see appendix 1), for example, these participants responded as follows:

“The competition was postponed due to unspecified circumstances.” (Ali, 15)

“For unspecified circumstances.” (Abdelkader, 18)

“Due to unspecified circumstances.” (Lahsen, 15)

The participants take straight from the text in the examples above; thus answering correctly.

Sub-theme 2.1: Inference Difficulty

Alternatively, and on the very same task, a difficulty with inference ability was simultaneously present in the participants’ answers; evident in a complete failure to make correct inferences, or making weak and lacking inferences instead of fully accurate ones. This difficulty was consistently found with all seven participants in answering at least one of the six questions of the task.

To the question inquiring the reason for a family’s gathering tradition; indicated in the reading passage (See appendix), as example, these participants responded as follows:

“Because it is a tradition. That is why Yacine’s family gathers to celebrate because of his grandfather’s old age.” (Abdelkader, 18)

“The grandfather is old, which makes transportation and walking in general difficult for him, and that is why the family gathers in his house to grant him the chance to meet the others and catch up with them.” (Ali, 15)

The participants stray from the simple evident answer (See appendix) in the examples above; thus answering incorrectly.

Theme 2: Logical Entailment

In the second task of the pragmatic assessment test: Analytical Reasoning; the participants were tested for their ability to check for the consistency of ideas or information in language. The participants were simply asked to judge certain premises depending on if they make sense in relation to a scenario or a situation. Through their answers; concerning the logic in the different statements, the concept of logical entailment was highlighted; present in the form of either a competence or a difficulty. The theme occurred with all of the involved participants, while its sub-themes differed in occurrence.

Figure 4.4 displays the frequency of Logical Entailment sub-themes.

Figure 4.4: A graph comparing the frequency of the Logical Entailment sub-themes.

Sub-theme 2.1: Logical Entailment Competence

The ability to make logical connections and confirm or deny statements by what other existing related statements entail came into view in the answers in Task 2 (See appendix) of the assessment test. Five out of seven participants were consistently able to correctly make the

connection between a premise and a conclusion in at least one out of three answers. The participants displayed the adequate use of the concept by confirming the truths in text and disproving of the nonsensical statements.

To the correct, logical conclusion of the premise: “All children of the neighborhood’s residents get invited to summer trips.”, stating that: “Soumia got invited to a summer trip. So she must be a child of a resident.”; these participants responded as follows:

“She was invited to a summer trip. It is correct.” (Marwa, 13)

“Yes. Soumia is from the neighborhood.” (Lahsen, 15)

“The conclusion is logical.” (Walid, 15)

The participants confirm the statement in the examples above; thus answering correctly.

Sub-theme 2.2: Logical Entailment Difficulty

In contrast to the logical entailment competence, the failure to correctly check for logical entailments dominated the answers of the second task in the assessment. All of the seven participants displayed a form of difficulty with following logical sequences or understanding the logic of a statement in the first place. The participants were not able to detect the logical inconsistency in some conclusions; even showing a complete absence of the concept in some cases.

To the incorrect, illogical conclusion to the premise: “Dates are fruits.”, stating: “This fruit is a date, so it must be delicious.”; these participants responded as follows:

“Dates are the tastiest fruit. Logically, it is delicious.” (Farouk, 15)

“Dates are considered one of the most important types of fruit, and it is a great cure for illnesses and it is rich in vitamins. That is why our prophet Mohamed advised us to have it.” (Abdelkader, 18)

“The fruit tastes very good, indeed. We all have had it already.” (Malek, 13)

The participants do not deny and correct the statement in the examples above, or even call attention to it being illogical; thus answering incorrectly.

Theme 3: Politeness and Social understanding

The theme of politeness and social understanding surfaced in the answers of the third task of the assessment test: Problem-Solving scenarios. The task evaluates the participants' capacity to respond in the most appropriate manner in social situations; by checking for their awareness and understanding of social nuances in the subtleties of language use. The concept of politeness was evident in either the participants' awareness of other people's *face* and their own, and performing face-saving acts, or the lack thereof. The theme occurred with all seven teenagers, and its sub-themes differed in occurrence.

Figure 4.5 displays the frequency of Politeness and Social Understanding sub-themes.

Figure 4.5: A graph comparing the frequency of the Politeness and Social Understanding sub-themes.

Sub-theme 3.1: Politeness Awareness

Posed with a social situation implying a problem in the third task of the assessment test; the participants were asked to propose an appropriate course of action or plan of communication to untangle the core of the situation including themselves and other people. The sub-theme emerged in this task; which was aimed at testing the teenagers' ability to understand the subtle social implications within language, their capacity to curate the appropriate reactions or responses to different social situations, and their awareness of the need to tend to those social implications in the first place. Six out of seven participants displayed the ability to understand social situations and respond to them in typical decency. This ability was evident in their attempts to either preserve the *face* of the person mentioned in the situation, or their own.

To a hypothetical problem detailing that the participants themselves had happened to dispose of one of their father's books by mistake; these participants responded as follows:

“I will face the situation, tell my father that I threw the books by accident, and apologize.”
(Malek, 13)

“I will tell him the truth and try to replace the book in any way possible.” (Ali, 15)

“I will face the situation by asking for forgiveness and not repeating the mistake once more, and

“I will go to the bookshop to buy him books to replace the lost books.” (Abdelkader, 18)

The participants address their mistake, and attempt to mend the situation, showing awareness for both the face of the person in the situation and their own; thus giving an appropriate answer.

Sub-theme 3.2: Politeness Difficulty

While they were able to comprehend what certain situations necessitated, the participants failed to understand the nature of other situations or think of proper responses to them. The sub-theme of Politeness Difficulty appeared in their difficulty to react appropriately to these social situations; and their neglect for the approaches that would be considered typical and most effective. Four out of seven participants showed difficulty with social understanding.

To a hypothetical problem detailing that a friend of the participant expressed feelings of frustration and sadness over a phone call, but without offering any clarifying details or explanations for the rant; these participants responded as follows:

“I will get rid of his frustration through playing and joking.” (Walid, 15)

“I too will express my feelings towards him. I will tell him everything I feel.” (Malek, 13)

“Do not be upset. Study harder.” (Lahsen, 15)

The participants failed to show understanding or attention for the friend’s feelings, or propose decent responses; thus giving an inappropriate answer.

Theme 4: Discourse Comprehension

The theme of Discourse Comprehension appeared in the participants’ answers on the fourth task of the pragmatic assessment test: Text-Based Dialogue Analysis. The task required the participants to analyze excerpts of different conversations between different people. The conversations were of different tones, and in different contexts, and the participants were asked

to detail their understanding of them. The theme occurred with all of the involved participants, and its sub-themes differed in frequency across admitted answers.

Figure 4.6 displays the frequency of Discourse Comprehension sub-themes.

Figure 4.6: A graph comparing the frequency of the Discourse Comprehension sub-themes.

Sub-theme 4.1: Discourse Comprehension Competence

The fourth task of the assessment test aimed to test the participants ability to understand conversation, detect the underlying implications of simple utterances in dialogue, and be aware of the context of said conversations. The Discourse Comprehension Competence sub-theme was observed with only four out of seven participants. The participants were able to provide a near-accurate digestion of some of the short exchanges in the task, as evident in their ability to grasp the general theme of those excerpts.

About a conversation, with casual undertones, between two co-workers, where one expresses exhaustion during their shift and the other suggests covering for them while they rest; these participants commented:

“In this dialogue between Amina and Marwa, Amina asks Marwa to rest because she is tired, and she will take care of the shop because she is worried about her health.” (Farouk, 15)

“A sentiment of friendship. They think of helping each other and they have a strong relationship.” (Oussama, 15)

The participants picked up on the central meaning of the interaction; thus answering correctly.

Sub-theme 4.2: Discourse Comprehension Difficulty

In the same task, the participants showed more difficulty than ability with discourse comprehension. The sub-theme of Discourse Comprehension Difficulty was present with six out of seven participants, dominating their answers. The participants failed to land on the actual meaning of the provided excerpts of dialogue; giving incorrect interpretations of them, and failing to simplify their understanding of the implied intentions, emotions or relationships of the people in the conversations.

About a conversation between a girl and her friend, where she reminds him of their teacher's upcoming birthday and the necessity to prepare something for it; these participants commented:

“Aim to surprise and bring happiness.” (Walid, 15)

“Layla is a trickster, using Omar's kindness to make him prepare a gift that's suitable for the teacher with her.” (Ali, 15)

“The teacher's birthday is next week but Omar had no idea of it being that soon. He has to plan something special for her, for example.” (Abdelkader, 18)

The participants failed to realize the girl's intentions, or the relationship between the conversing two; thus answering incorrectly.

Theme 5: Relationship with General Meaning

The way the participants made sense of the language used in the pragmatic assessment test overall, and the display of that understanding, in all of its different degrees and capacities, was labeled as the theme: Relationship with General meaning. Although the theme appeared in the answers of several different tasks, it was most evident in the fifth task of the pragmatic test: Critical Reading. The task presented the participants with short passages of text entailing a central main idea, and required them to pinpoint that exact principal meaning of the passages. The theme occurred with seven out of seven participants, and differed in frequency with its sub-themes.

Figure 4.7 displays the frequency of Relationship with General Meaning sub-themes.

Figure 4.7: A graph comparing the frequency of the Relationship with General Meaning sub-themes.

Sub-theme 5.1: Divergent Relationship with Meaning

Throughout the test, the participants showed a unique relationship with meaning which cannot be exactly labeled as a typical understanding of it, nor a total failure to comprehend it; but rather a different process of reaching correct conclusions, and a different way of expressing that final understanding. This diversion occurred with all seven participants, and was evident in the superficiality of understanding some passages, specific or literal interpretations of meaning, and the presence of irrelevant or additional information in the answers. This relationship with meaning is different from a simple general difficulty with it, and was considered due to the context of autism. There have been many instances of this sub-theme in the data, as shown in Table 4.8.

Task	Requirement	Provided Passage	Participant's Answer	Type of Divergent Understanding
Reading Comprehension	Making a correct inference to answer a question	“Right after Ramadan, Yacine’s family always has a big gathering in his grandfather’s home. Due to old age, he is diabetic, so he misses out on most of the desserts.”	“The grandfather is old, which makes transportation and walking in general difficult for him, and that is why the family gathers in his house to grant him the chance to meet the others and catch up with them.” (<i>Ali, 15</i>)	Irrelevant/ Additional information.
Text-Based Dialogue Analysis	Analyzing a conversation	“ Layla: "Don't forget about our teacher's birthday next week." Omar: "Birthday? I had no idea it was this soon! We should plan something special for her.””	“When the teacher comes and sees, she is surprised and she thanks them. They eat and drink and play and the party is all joy.” (<i>Malek, 13</i>)	Superficial Understanding
Analytical Reasoning	Checking for logical consistency	“ Premise: "All children of the neighborhood's residents get invited to summer trips." Conclusion: "Soumia got invited to a summer trip. So she must be a child of a resident.””	“The conclusion is incorrect because the invited people are the neighborhood's boys, and Soumia is a girl, not a boy.” (<i>Ali, 15</i>)	Specific/ Literal Interpretation

Table 4.7: Instances of the Divergent Relationship with Meaning sub-theme.

Sub-theme 5.2: General Difficulty with Context

This sub-theme was, in contrast to the Divergent Relationship with Meaning, only present in the fifth task of the assessment test; where it was required to investigate the general context specifically. Two out of seven participants had a general difficulty with meaning. The difficulty

was not related to a divergent understanding, but simply associated with a failure to fully comprehend the context of the passage provided in the Critical Reading task. In the instances in which it appeared, this sub-theme represented an obliviousness to context, and an inability to find the main and essential pieces of information in the texts.

When presented with a small passage and expected to answer posed questions; one participant failed to provide an answer entirely, while the other performed as follows:

Passage	Question	Central Idea	Participant's Answer
<p>“The student council was skeptical about the school’s new rules. Most students expressed concern and disappointment for the new and strict decisions, while others welcomed the change hesitantly, in hope for a positive turn.”</p>	<p>“What can you infer about the students' reactions to the school’s new rules?”</p>	<p>“There was a general feeling of hesitance and unease expressed by all students, including the ones willing to give the change a chance, indicating that the new rules may have been surprising, unusual or too stern for the regular student.”</p>	<p>“The students care for positive rules.” <i>(Lahsen ,15)</i></p>

Table 4.8: Example of the General Difficulty with Context sub-theme.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

This study investigated the pragmatic abilities of seven Algerian teenagers with ASD, aged from 13 to 18 years old. A pragmatic assessment test developed especially for this research was used to collect written data from the participants. The test contained questions which aimed to reveal specific pragmatic characteristics of the participants’ language, based on the pragmatic concepts: *Reference and Inference, Presupposition and Entailment, Politeness, and Discourse*. Through the participants’ answers, five major themes and ten sub-themes emerged from the thematic-analysis of the data.

4.3.1 Themes and Sub-themes

The themes which emerged from the written answers of the seven autistic participants each referred to a pragmatic field of ability, while the sub-themes referred to either a competence in that ability, whether passable or perfect, a difficulty, or lack thereof altogether. In their answers, the participants displayed their own use and understanding of language, which contained the instances of the presence or absence of the abilities when needed or expected. In other words, the themes and sub-themes are a description of the participants' language, but they are also an assessment of their use of pragmatic skills.

4.3.2 Theme 1: Reference and Inference

The ability to make inferences about what is read or heard is one the key elements of pragmatic understanding. According to Yule (1996), this ability refers to the person's mission to interpret the exact intended entities referred to by a speaker, in order to follow through conveniently and quickly enough in conversation, or to grasp the direction of a text in reading. The reference and inference theme surfaced in the answers to the first task of the pragmatic test: *Reading Comprehension*. The participants were expected to read through very short and simplified passages which tell events, and then remember stated key information, and make inferences about the statements to answer the questions in the task.

Sub-themes: Inference Competence and Inference Difficulty

The theme occurred with all participants, meaning that seven out of seven of the teenagers either displayed an ability to make correct inferences, or a difficulty in making inferences. Additionally, all seven participants showed both a difficulty and a competence in making inferences, depending on the question. The occurrences of inference difficulty are consistent with the findings of Loukusa et al (2007), which state that high-functioning individuals with ASD perform poorly on context-related tasks, especially in reference and inference making. However, since the participants showed both sides of the Inference ability, the results carry additional implications. Firstly, the answers where the Inference Competence appeared were mostly to a particularly clear and simply formulated reading passage:

Text: "The annual poetry competition starts at around 10:00 a.m. in the conference building. Due to unspecified circumstances, it was postponed for a couple of hours."

Question: "Why was it postponed?"

Answers: "The competition was postponed due to unspecified circumstances." (Ali, 15)

"For unspecified circumstances." (Abdelkader, 18)

"Due to unspecified circumstances." (Lahsen, 15)

Although the task was created with the knowledge that autistic people generally have difficulties with language, thus simplified for accuracy and to focus on specific pragmatic skills, the level of difficulty of the passage is ideal for testing the participants' ability to remember key information and recall it. The accurate answers provided by the participants may have been due to the simplicity and clarity of the passage, but they also suggest a capacity to make inferences in passages which deal with very few events or ideas at the same time. Moreover, the correct answers indicate a tendency to make accurate inferences when the targeted piece of information is a central one in the provided passage. To a different passages, some participants answered as follows:

Passage: "Right after Ramadan, Yacine's family always has a big gathering in his grandfather's home.

Due to old age, he is diabetic, so he misses out on most of the desserts."

Question: "Who is diabetic?"

Answers: "The grandfather is the diabetic." (Oussama, 16)

"The diabetic is the grandfather; because of his old age." (Farouk, 15)

"The grandfather." (Abdelkader, 18)

4.3.3 Theme 2: Logical Entailment

The logical connection between two pieces of information, or two pairs of sentences, is referred to as an Entailment: The attached knowledge in the middle of two truths. The ability to spot logical inconsistencies is essential to the individual's general understanding of conversations, ensuring the detection of incorrect or nonsensical information and the distinction between them and actual truths. The Logical Entailment theme was apparent in the second task of the pragmatic test: *Analytical Reasoning*. The participants were presented with pairs of premises and conclusions, and asked whether they fit together or make any sense, thus, the participants were required to employ logic to analyze the presented statements and comment on them.

Sub-themes: Logical Entailment Ability and Logical Entailment Difficulty

The theme was found with all seven participants, indicating the possibility of competence in Entailment, or a difficulty with it. All seven participants showed the ability of logical entailment, successfully dissecting the logic of certain premise-conclusion pairs. Meanwhile, five out of the seven teenagers showed a difficulty with logical entailment, completely missing the logic of the pairs they answered questions on, or judging them incorrectly. In the case of logical entailment difficulty, the inability to utilize context to aid with the linking of ideas or detect logical connections or inconsistencies is in line with the findings of Noveck, I et al (2007). The participants showed a disregard or an unawareness for contextual information which could have guided them with their observations and comments.

Passage: Premise: "If it doesn't stop raining, some of the roads will be blocked"

Conclusion: "Some roads were blocked today, so it must have rained heavily and nonstop."

Comments: "The conclusion is logical." (Ali, 15)

"Correct." (Lahsen, 15)

"The roads should be closed because the more it rains, the bigger the danger." (Farouk, 15)

Additionally, the literal interpretation of a particular premise was noticed with several participants. Although that could be attributed to the phrasing of the premise, the vagueness of the sentence was an intentional increase of difficulty decided by the researcher to evaluate the participants' capacity to navigate all logical possibilities and answer as closely to the ideal answer as possible. Thus, it could also be an indicator of a rigidness in linguistic understanding, a common index of the divergent thinking which comes with autism.

Passage: Premise: "All children of the neighborhood's residents get invited to summer trips."

Conclusion: "Souria got invited to a summer trip. So she must be a child of a resident."

Comments: "The conclusion doesn't suit the premise because she is a girl." (Oussama, 16)

"Soumia shouldn't be invited because the summer trip is for the neighborhood's boys only." (Farouk, 15)

"The conclusion is incorrect because the invited people are the neighborhood's boys, and Soumia is a girl, not a boy." (Ali, 15)

4.3.4 Theme 3: Politeness and Social Understanding.

Social difficulties are a hallmark of ASD across all the spectrum. The social-pragmatic aspect of language, however, is specific to the ability to use language in order to communicate as effectively and as socially-appropriate as possible. The awareness of social distance and one's own face and the other's are crucial for decent social interactions. In the current study, the theme of Politeness and Social Understanding was found in the answers of the third task of the pragmatic assessment test: Problem-Solving Scenarios. The participants were expected to understand descriptions of certain social situations well enough to detect the social implications within them and respond accordingly, thus handling a socially-related issue appropriately with the right considerations.

Sub-themes: Politeness Competence and Politeness Difficulty

The theme was evident in all seven participants' answers, manifesting in either a competence in the concept of Politeness, or a clear difficulty with it. Six out of seven participants showed a good ability to handle social understanding, while merely four out of seven participants displayed an incompetence in social understanding. Consistent with Anderson's (1990) findings, in the instances of Politeness difficulty, the participants' answers bordered on irrelevance.

Problem: "Your friend expresses frustration over a phone call, but never specifies the reason for it, and simply sounds sad. How would you approach the situation?"

Approach: "I will try to solve his problems, and ask for help." (Oussama, 16)

"I will get rid of his frustration through playing and joking." (Walid, 15)

"I too will express my feelings towards him. I will tell him everything I feel." (Malek, 13)

Although there was a clear struggle with fully grasping the implications and nuances in the presented scenarios of the task, shown by the participants, which aligns with Dewey and Evard's (1974), and Ball's (1978) findings, the majority of the participants were able to provide acceptable answers which held good understanding of social customs and appropriate social decisions. This could be due to the deeply communal and social culture of the participants' country, where it is expected to keep up with customs of politeness, and the need to anticipate and analyze people's emotions, thoughts, and expressions in interactions is constant. Additionally, all of the participants go to a public educational institution alongside

typically-developing children, and do not introduce themselves with the autistic label often despite fully identifying with it. This implies an environmental and cultural influence, or rather pressure, on the participants' Politeness ability.

Problem: "Your friend expresses frustration over a phone call, but never specifies the reason for it, and simply sounds sad. How would you approach the situation?"

Approach: "I will try to lighten it up for him without asking him about the reason and getting into his private life, fearing that he will be displeased with me. For example, I will try to remind him of some of the prophet's sayings as well as verses from the Quran which show God's wisdom and his mercy." (Ali, 15)

"I will console him a little with comforting words and try to know the reason for his sadness to help him and draw him out of the psychological crisis that he is passing through." (Abdelkader, 18)

4.3.5 Theme 4: Discourse Comprehension

Discourse comprehension entails the ability to understand conversational speech or written text based on the linguistic structures which it is made up of, the general context, and the alignment and organization of the ideas presented within. Moreover, social context and the cultural influence on language makes up a big part of discourse. This ability enables the individual to take part in different interactions by understanding what is being communicated simply through its superficial structure, and necessitates a familiarity with the ways people communicate in their environment. This ability was put to test in the fourth task of the assessment test: Text-Based Dialogue Analysis. The participants were presented with excerpts from daily conversations between two characters, and asked to provide their opinions on their intentions, relationships, or emotions.

Sub-themes: Discourse Comprehension Competence and Discourse Comprehension Difficulty

The theme of Discourse Comprehension appeared with all of the seven participants. Six out of seven participants showed competence in discourse comprehensions, providing accurate observations and assumptions about the presented conversations in the task, while four out of seven participants showed a difficulty with discourse comprehension, either assuming wrongly about the characters' relationships and intentions, or misunderstanding the general meaning and context of the interactions altogether. The ability to process conversations and arrive at passable

conclusions about the people involved, the true implications of their utterances, and the context of a situation implies a familiarity with discourse in daily life. This could be, again, attributed to the social nature of Algerian society and the tendency for Algerian parents and peers to encourage the children and teenagers to socialize. Additionally, it could suggest a familiarity with discourse through media consumption, i.e. books or tv shows.

Conversation: Ali: "Did you hear about the new job openings at the private school nearby?"

Fatima: "Yes, I did. I'm considering applying for the assistant teacher position. You should too."

Observations: "They are colleagues and friends, and they help each other." (Oussama, 16)

"Motivation" (Walid, 15)

On the other hand, the cases in which difficulty with discourse was evidence were characterized by extreme misunderstanding, either due to an inability to recognize the context, or a failure to assume the states of mind of the conversing characters. This is consistent with Jafari. P (2019) and Serber and Wilson's (1986) findings on the relationship between Theory of Mind and autism.

Conversation: Ali: "Did you hear about the new job openings at the private school nearby?"

Fatima: "Yes, I did. I'm considering applying for the assistant teacher position. You should too."

Observations: "The two should apply and help each other. Help brings trust and friendship for everyone." (Malek, 13)

"Fatima is a lying and deceitful girl, because if she truly wanted to apply to the vacant assistant teacher's position, then why did she ask Ali to apply too?" (Ali, 15)

4.3.6 Theme 5: Relationship with General Meaning

Unlike the previous themes, the Relationship with General Meaning, which refers to the individual's interaction with language and their paths of thought which lead them to understanding and using language, surfaced all over the participants answers to the pragmatic test, mainly due to the fact that the participants' use and understanding of language is indeed in everything they wrote. The average individual has a direct relationship with meaning, developed and obtained as they age typically within their social environment, but individuals with autism

perceive and create meaning differently, as well as use language in a unique way due to their difficulty in realizing the already existing social schemas dictating its use.

Sub-themes: Divergent Relationship with Meaning and General Difficulty with Context

The autistic relationship with meaning was labeled into two sub-themes in this study, neither expressing a definitive competence or incompetence. Although the fifth and final task of the assessment test: Critical Reading, which expected the participants to search for non-given information in short passages and answer a general understanding question, intended to investigate the autistic relationship with meaning specifically, the entirety of the test contained samples of the participants' use and understanding of language, and held valuable instances of autism-specific characteristics. The general difficulty with context, referring to a simple inability to understand general meaning, only occurred with two participants. This does not imply that the participants do not have difficulties with context, as that was observed in collocation with the other previous themes, but rather that their difficulty with context is not a general one, and that it is related to other factors, and possibly even stems for them.

Passage: "The student council was skeptical about the school's new rules. Most students expressed concern and disappointment for the new and strict decisions, while others welcomed the change hesitantly, in hope for a positive turn."

Question: "What can you infer about the students' reactions to the school's new rules?"

Answer: "The students care for positive rules." (Lahsen ,15)

Consistent with Tager-Flusberg's (1992, 1993, 1997) findings, the relationship with language and meaning, which was observed through the participants' answers, is a unique and divergent one, characterized by literal interpretations, the mention of apparently irrelevant or additional information, superficial understanding of statements and considering them direct, and the specific focus or fixation on singular elements within sentences or conversations. This may suggest that some areas of autistic communication which are considered deficits may simply be mere differences which are not logical or convenient to the typical majority. This is backed up by the instances of Divergent Relationship with Meaning along with the difficulties with pragmatic concepts in the data. Specific instances of the divergent relationship with meaning are labeled in the following table:

Task	Requirement	Provided Passage	Participant's Answer	Type of Divergent Understanding
Reading Comprehension	Making a correct inference to answer a question	“Right after Ramadan, Yacine’s family always has a big gathering in his grandfather’s home. Due to old age, he is diabetic, so he misses out on most of the desserts.”	“The grandfather is old, which makes transportation and walking in general difficult for him, and that is why the family gathers in his house to grant him the chance to meet the others and catch up with them.” <i>(Ali, 15)</i>	Irrelevant/ Additional information.
Text-Based Dialogue Analysis	Analyzing a conversation	“ Layla: "Don't forget about our teacher's birthday next week." Omar: "Birthday? I had no idea it was this soon! We should plan something special for her.””	“When the teacher comes and sees, she is surprised and she thanks them. They eat and drink and play and the party is all joy.” <i>(Malek, 13)</i>	Superficial Understanding
Analytical Reasoning	Checking for logical consistency	“ Premise: "All children of the neighborhood's residents get invited to summer trips." Conclusion: "Soumia got invited to a summer trip. So she must be a child of a resident.””	“The conclusion is incorrect because the invited people are the neighborhood's boys, and Soumia is a girl, not a boy.” <i>(Ali, 15)</i>	Specific/ Literal Interpretation

Table 5.1: Instances of the Divergent Relationship with Meaning sub-theme.

4.4. Implications of Findings

The findings of the current study provided a multi-concept perspective on pragmatic assessment in ASD. In contrast to previous approaches, this study encapsulated the different facets and characteristics of its participants' profiles of pragmatic ability, detailing areas of competence and difficulty, and highlighting areas in between. Several pragmatic aspects of ability were evident in all of the participants' answers, suggesting that pragmatic ability is composed of multiple nuanced details, and cannot simply be measured during a score-based brief process. The findings also showcase diversity in the participants' profiles, as they contain both instances of intact pragmatic ability and pragmatic incompetence, suggesting that pragmatic ability differs from one autistic individual to the other in terms of which abilities are more prominent and in-use than the others, and not in terms of strength and weakness. Finally, the pragmatic assessment test which was specifically developed for this study, and the qualitative approach to assessing the pragmatic skills of the seven Algerian autistic teenagers, proved to be efficient in providing in-depth details and insights into the individual expressions of language use in autistic people.

4.5 Summary:

The findings presented in this chapter detailed the unique pragmatic profiles of seven Algerian teenagers with ASD and the characteristics of their language use and understanding. The results were linked to the previous findings and key theories in the field, and also compared to them. Examples to back up the claims stated in the discussion were provided for each section. The themes were remarked to be complementary and related; and, most importantly, helped provide answers to the previously set research questions of the current study.

In the following chapter, the process of the study is concluded. The contributions of the study are listed and detailed in relation to previous works, the limitations of the research are mentioned, and suggestions for future research and development are provided.

Chapter Five

Conclusion

5 CHAPTER FIVE: CONCLUSION

5.1 Overview

In this chapter, the study's process and findings are summarized and contextualized. This final chapter reflects on the contributions of the research, acknowledges its limitations, and provides suggestions for future research. By synthesizing the results and considering their implications, this chapter aims to offer a comprehensive conclusion to the study.

5.2 Restatement of Research Questions

The current study is an investigation of the pragmatic abilities of seven Algerian autistic teenagers. The study used a pragmatic-concepts-based assessment test to evaluate the participants on several pragmatic language skills. The current study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. How are the pragmatic abilities of Algerian autistic teenagers?
2. Do the pragmatic profiles of Algerian autistic teenagers show distinct individual patterns?
3. What do the pragmatic profiles of the Algerian autistic teenagers imply about the methodology used to achieve them?

5.3 Summary of Findings

The study investigated the pragmatic abilities of Algerian autistic teenagers using a mixed-method approach. Through a thematic analysis of the data which was collected from a pragmatic assessment test, five key themes emerged: Reference and Inference, Logical Entailment, Politeness and Social Understanding, Discourse Comprehension, and Relationship with General Meaning. Each theme revealed varying levels of competence and difficulty among the participants, highlighting both their strengths and areas needing support.

5.4 Contributions to Existing Knowledge

This research contributes to the field of pragmatic assessment in autism by providing a nuanced understanding of pragmatic abilities in autistic individuals. Unlike previous studies that often used quantitative methods or focused on limited aspects of pragmatics, this study employed a mixed-method approach to capture the complexity of language use among autistic teenagers. The findings offer new insights into how these individuals navigate and interpret language,

underscoring the variability in pragmatic abilities and challenging the notion of a uniform profile for autistic individuals. The development of a pragmatic-concepts-based assessment test specifically tailored for this study is a significant contribution. It allows for a detailed exploration of pragmatic skills beyond what is typically measured by traditional assessments. Additionally, the study highlights the importance of considering cultural and environmental factors in understanding pragmatic abilities, as evidenced by the influence of Algerian societal norms on participants' responses.

5.6 Limitations of the Study

Despite its contributions, this study undeniably has its limitations:

Sample Size: The study involved a small sample of seven participants, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. A larger sample could provide a more comprehensive understanding of pragmatic abilities across different autistic individuals.

Time: Due to tight deadlines, certain aspects of the research, such as extended data collection or in-depth analysis, were constrained. This limited time frame may have impacted the depth of exploration into some areas, and future studies with more time allocated could provide a more comprehensive analysis.

5.7 Recommendations for Future Research

Based on the findings and limitations of this study, several recommendations for future research are proposed:

Sample Size and Diversity: Future studies should include a larger and more diverse sample to enhance the generalizability of the findings. Exploring different age groups, gender, and autism spectrum levels could provide a broader understanding of pragmatic abilities.

Cross-Cultural Studies: Investigating pragmatic abilities in autistic individuals from various cultural backgrounds will help determine the influence of cultural factors on language use and understanding. This could lead to more culturally inclusive assessment tools and interventions.

Longitudinal Studies: Longitudinal research tracking pragmatic abilities over time could provide insights into developmental trajectories and the effectiveness of interventions aimed at improving pragmatic skills.

5.8 Practical Implications

The findings of this study have practical implications for educators, clinicians, and policymakers:

Educational Interventions: Tailored educational programs that address specific pragmatic challenges identified in this study can help autistic individuals develop better communication skills. Educational strategies should be individualized and consider the unique needs of each student.

Clinical Practice: Clinicians should incorporate findings related to pragmatic abilities into their assessments and interventions. Understanding the nuanced nature of pragmatic skills can lead to more effective therapeutic approaches.

Policy Development: Policymakers should consider the diverse needs of autistic individuals when developing support services and resources. Ensuring that interventions and educational materials are culturally sensitive and adaptable can improve outcomes for autistic individuals.

REFERENCES

- Adams, C. (2002). Practitioner Review: The assessment of language pragmatics. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 43(8), 973–987. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1469-7610.00226>
- Adams, C., Lockton, E., Freed, J., Gaile, J., Earl, G., McBean, K., Nash, M., Green, J., Vail, A., & Law, J. (2012). The Social Communication Intervention Project: a randomized controlled trial of the effectiveness of speech and language therapy for school-age children who have pragmatic and social communication problems with or without autism spectrum disorder. *International Journal of Language & Communication Disorders*, 47(3), 233–244. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-6984.2011.00146.x>
- Adrien, J. L., Ornitz, E., Barthelemy, C., Sauvage, D., & Lelord, G. (1987). The presence or absence of certain behaviors associated with infantile autism in severely retarded autistic and nonautistic retarded children and very young normal children. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 17(3), 407–416. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf01487069>
- Ambridge, B., Bidgood, A., & Thomas, K. (2020). Disentangling syntactic, semantic and pragmatic impairments in ASD: Elicited production of passives. *Journal of Child Language*, 48(1), 184–201. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0305000920000215>
- Andrés-Roqueta, C., Flores-Buils, R., & Igualada, A. (2024). Validation of PleaseApp: a digital tool for the assessment of receptive pragmatic abilities in children with neurodevelopmental disorders. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 15.
- Arani Kashani, Z. (2019). The translation and determination of psychometric properties of the Persian version of the “TOPL-2” in children aged 9 and 14. *Function and Disability Journal*, 2(1), 77-82.
- Arcara, Giorgio & Bambini, Valentina. (2016). A Test for the Assessment of Pragmatic Abilities and Cognitive Substrates (APACS): Normative Data and Psychometric Properties. *Frontiers in Psychology*. 7. 10.3389/fpsyg.2016.00070.

- Association, A. P. (2021). *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5)*. American Psychiatric Publishing.
- Bachman, Lyle. (2000). Modern language testing at the turn of the century: assuring that what we count counts. *Language Testing*, 17, 1-42. 10.1191/026553200675041464.
- Balestro, J. I., & Fernandes, F. D. M.. (2019). Caregivers' perception of children with Autism Spectrum Disorder regarding to the communicative profile of their children after a communicative orientation program, 31(1), e20170222. <https://doi.org/10.1590/2317-1782/20182018222>
- Bardovi-Harlig, K., & Shin, S. (2014). Expanding Traditional Testing Measures with Tasks from L2 Pragmatics Research. ResearchGate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/299673192_Expanding_Traditional_Testing_Measures_with_Tasks_from_L2_Pragmatics_Research
- Baron-Cohen, S. (1988). Social and pragmatic deficits in autism: Cognitive or affective? *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 18(3), 379–402. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02212194>
- Baron-Cohen, S., Leslie, A. M., & Frith, U. (1985). Does the autistic child have a “theory of mind”? *Cognition*, 21(1), 37–46. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-0277\(85\)90022-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-0277(85)90022-8)
- Baron-Cohen, S. (1989). The Autistic Child's Theory of Mind: a Case of Specific Developmental Delay. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 30(2), 285–297. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-7610.1989.tb00241.x>
- Brown, P., & Levinson, S. C. (1978, 1987). *Politeness Some universals in Language usage*. Cambridge Cambridge University Press. - References - Scientific Research Publishing. (n.d.). <https://www.scirp.org/reference/referencespapers?referenceid=1355363>

Burton, R. S. (1985). PRINCIPLES OF PRAGMATICS, Geoffrey N. Leech. London and New York: Longman, 1983. pp. 250. *Studies in Second Language Acquisition*, 7(1), 112–113. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0272263100005210>

Clark, M. J. (n.d.). Social Differences of Adolescents with High-Functioning Autism and Asperger's Syndrome. The Keep. https://thekeep.eiu.edu/honors_theses/25/

Clarke, V., Braun, V. and Hayfield, N. (2015) Thematic Analysis. In: Smith, J.A., Ed., *Qualitative Psychology: A Practical Guide to Research Methods*, SAGE Publications, London, 222-248.

Colle, L., Baron-Cohen, S. & Hill, J. Do Children with Autism have a Theory of Mind? A Non-verbal Test of Autism vs. Specific Language Impairment. *J Autism Dev Disord* 37, 716–723 (2007). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10803-006-0198-7>

Creswell, J. W. (2007). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches* (2nd ed.). Sage Publications, Inc.

Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Qualitative inquiry & research design: Choosing among five approaches* (4th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Cridland, E. K., Jones, S. C., Stoyles, G., Caputi, P., & Magee, C. A. (2016). Families living with autism spectrum disorder. *Focus on Autism and Other Developmental Disabilities*, 31(3), 196–207. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1088357615583466>

Crystal, D. (1998). Sense: the final frontier. *Child Language Teaching and Therapy*, 14(1), 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.1177/026565909801400101>

Cummings, L. (2011). Pragmatic disorders and their social impact. *Pragmatics and Society*, 2(1), 17–36. <https://doi.org/10.1075/ps.2.1.02cum>

- Deliens, G., Papastamou, F., Ruytenbeek, N. et al. Selective Pragmatic Impairment in Autism Spectrum Disorder: Indirect Requests Versus Irony. *J Autism Dev Disord* 48, 2938–2952 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10803-018-3561-6>
- Denzin, N. K. (2008). *Strategies of qualitative inquiry*. SAGE.
- Dewey, M. A., & Everard, M. P. (1974). The near-normal autistic adolescent: Nonreciprocal speech. *Journal of Autism & Childhood Schizophrenia*, 4(4), 348–356. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02105378>
- Dolata, J. K., Suarez, S., Calamé, B., & Fombonne, E. (2022). Pragmatic language markers of autism diagnosis and severity. *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders*, 94, 101970. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rasd.2022.101970>
- Dolata, J. K., Suarez, S., Calamé, B., & Fombonne, E. (2022b). Pragmatic language markers of autism diagnosis and severity. *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders*, 94, 101970. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rasd.2022.101970>
- Diken, O. (2019). Describing and comparing pragmatic language skills of Turkish students with typical development and inclusive education students with mild intellectual disability. *International Journal of Progressive Education*, 15(2), 157–166. <https://doi.org/10.29329/ijpe.2019.189.11>
- Eisenberg, L. (1956). THE AUTISTIC CHILD IN ADOLESCENCE. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 112(8), 607–612. <https://doi.org/10.1176/ajp.112.8.607>
- Gee, James. (2010). *An Introduction to Discourse Analysis: Theory and Method*. 10.4324/9780203847886.
- Ghafar, Zanyar. (2023). Evaluation Research: A Comparative Analysis of Qualitative and Quantitative Research Methods. *Middle East Research Journal of Linguistics and Literature*. V3. 25-32. [10.36348/merjll.2023.v03i02.25](https://doi.org/10.36348/merjll.2023.v03i02.25).

- Guest, Greg & Fleming, Paul. (2015). Mixed Methods Research. 10.4135/9781483398839.n19.
- Happé, F. G. (1993). Communicative competence and theory of mind in autism: A test of relevance theory. *Cognition*, 48(2), 101–119. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-0277\(93\)90026-r](https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-0277(93)90026-r)
- Happé, F., & Frith, U. (1995). Theory of mind in autism. In Springer eBooks (pp. 177–197). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4899-1286-2_10
- Helland, W. A., Aaland, E., Furebotn, K. L., Nilsen, J., Pettersen, H., Roe, A. L., Wathne, A. K. S., & Morken, F. (2024). Investigating pragmatic abilities in 5- to 7-year-old Norwegian children: A study using the Pragma test. *First Language*, 44(3), 264–281. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01427237241239114>
- Holloway, R. (2018). *Asperger’s children: Psychodynamics, Aetiology, Diagnosis, and Treatment*. Routledge.
- Hudson, G. (2000). *Essentials of Introductory Linguistics*. USA Blackwell Publishers. -
References - Scientific Research Publishing. (n.d.). <https://www.scirp.org/reference/referencespapers?referenceid=2215234>
- Jenkins, R. (n.d.). *The Effect of Familiarity on Joint Attention in Children with ASD*. eGrove. https://egrove.olemiss.edu/hon_thesis/1088/
- Kanner, L. (1943). Autistic disturbances of affective contact.
- Karim, M. A. (2017). *Culture and Discourse.pdf*. Iium. https://www.academia.edu/32060650/Culture_and_Discourse_pdf
- Kerbel, D., & Grunwell, P. (1998). A study of idiom comprehension in children with semantic-pragmatic difficulties. Part II: Between-groups results and discussion. *International Journal of Language & Communication Disorders*, 33(1), 23–44. <https://doi.org/10.1080/136828298247910>

- Lam, Y. G., & Yeung, S. S. S. (2012). Towards a convergent account of pragmatic language deficits in children with high-functioning autism: Depicting the phenotype using the Pragmatic Rating Scale. *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders*, 6(2), 792–797. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rasd.2011.08.004>
- Lee, A., Hobson, R. P., & Chiat, S. (1994). I, you, me, and autism: An experimental study. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 24(2), 155–176. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf02172094>
- Locke, John. (1997). A Theory of Neurolinguistic Development. *Brain and language*. 58. 265-326. [10.1006/brln.1997.1791](https://doi.org/10.1006/brln.1997.1791).
- Lord, C. (1990). A Cognitive Behavioral Model for the Treatment of Social-Communicative Deficits in Adolescents with Autism. In Springer eBooks (pp. 155–174). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4615-3734-2_11
- Lord, C., Bristol, M. M., & Schopler, E. (1993). Early Intervention for Children with Autism and Related Developmental Disorders. In Springer eBooks (pp. 199–221). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4899-2441-4_10
- Loukusa, S., Leinonen, E., Kuusikko, S., Jussila, K., Mattila, M., Ryder, N., Ebeling, H., & Moilanen, I. (2006). Use of Context in Pragmatic Language Comprehension by Children with Asperger Syndrome or High-Functioning Autism. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 37(6), 1049–1059. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10803-006-0247-2>
- Loveland, K. A., Landry, S. H., Hughes, S. O., Hall, S. K., & McEvoy, R. E. (1988). Speech acts and the pragmatic deficits of autism. *Journal of Speech Language and Hearing Research*, 31(4), 593–604. <https://doi.org/10.1044/jshr.3104.593>

Measuring pragmatic language in speakers with autism spectrum disorders: Comparing the children's communication checklist--2 and the test of pragmatic language. (2010). PubMed. [https://doi.org/10.1044/1058-0360\(2010/09-0011](https://doi.org/10.1044/1058-0360(2010/09-0011)

Miranda, A., Berenguer, C., Baixauli, I., & Roselló, B. (2023). Childhood language skills as predictors of social, adaptive and behavior outcomes of adolescents with autism spectrum disorder. *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders*, 103, 102143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rasd.2023.102143>

Miranda, A., Berenguer, C., Baixauli, I., & Roselló, B. (2023b). Childhood language skills as predictors of social, adaptive and behavior outcomes of adolescents with autism spectrum disorder. *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders*, 103, 102143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rasd.2023.102143>

Mäkinen, L., Loukusa, S., Leinonen, E., Moilanen, I., Ebeling, H., & Kunnari, S. (2014). Characteristics of narrative language in autism spectrum disorder: Evidence from the Finnish. *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders*, 8(8), 987–996. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rasd.2014.05.001>

Norbury, C. F., & Bishop, D. V. M. (2002). Inferential processing and story recall in children with communication problems: A comparison of specific language impairment, pragmatic language impairment and high-functioning autism. *International Journal of Language & Communication Disorders*, 37(3), 227–251. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13682820210136269>

Palinkas, L.A., et al. (2015) Purposeful Sampling for Qualitative Data Collection and Analysis in Mixed Method Implementation Research. *Administration and Policy in Mental Health and Mental Health Services Research*, 42, 533-544. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10488-013-0528-y>

Papalia, D., Olds, S., & Feldman, R. (2008). *Human development*. McGraw-Hill Humanities/Social Sciences/Languages.

- Peristeri, E., Frantzidis, C. A., & Andreou, M. (2024). Reading comprehension differences between children with Autism Spectrum Disorder and low cognitive abilities and children with Autism Spectrum Disorder and intact cognitive skills: the roles of decoding, fluency and morphosyntax. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 15. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1357590>
- Pijnacker, J., Hagoort, P., Buitelaar, J., Teunisse, J., & Geurts, B. (2008). Pragmatic Inferences in High-Functioning Adults with Autism and Asperger Syndrome. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 39(4), 607–618. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10803-008-0661-8>
- Priya, A. (2020). Case study Methodology of Qualitative Research: Key attributes and navigating the conundrums in its application. *Sociological Bulletin*, 70(1), 94–110. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0038022920970318>
- Prutting, C. A., & Kirchner, D. M. (1987). A clinical appraisal of the pragmatic aspects of language. *Journal of Speech & Hearing Disorders*, 52(2), 105–119. <https://doi.org/10.1044/jshd.5202.105>
- Rahman, F., Yuzar, E., & Zhou, W. (2023). Developing an online test battery for testing EFL pragmatic competence: What can it tell us? *Scope Journal of English Language Teaching*, 8(1), 72. <https://doi.org/10.30998/scope.v8i1.17418>
- Rudy, L. J. (2024, January 10). Understanding the three levels of autism. Verywell Health. <https://www.verywellhealth.com/what-are-the-three-levels-of-autism-260233>
- Ryan Blackwell, Gemma. (2018). Introduction to positivism, interpretivism and critical theory. *Nurse Researcher*. 25. 14-20. [10.7748/nr.2018.e1466](https://doi.org/10.7748/nr.2018.e1466).
- Sacco K, Angeleri R, Bosco F.M, Colle L, Mate D, Bara B.G. (2008). Assessment Battery for Communication — ABaCo: A new Instrument for the Evaluation of Pragmatic Abilities. *Journal of Cognitive Science*, 9(2), 111–157. <https://doi.org/10.17791/jcs.2008.9.2.111>

- Savtak, G. A., Diken, I. H., Ardiç, A., & Gilliam, J. E. (2014). Adaptation and Examining Psychometrical Properties of Pragmatic Language Skills Inventory (PLSI) in Turkey.
- Setia, M. (2016). Methodology series module 3: Cross-sectional studies. *Indian Journal of Dermatology*, 61(3), 261. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0019-5154.182410>
- Sofronoff, K., Attwood, T., Hinton, S. et al. A Randomized Controlled Trial of a Cognitive Behavioural Intervention for Anger Management in Children Diagnosed with Asperger Syndrome. *J Autism Dev Disord* 37, 1203–1214 (2007). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10803-006-0262-3>
- Sperber, D., & Wilson, D. (1986). *Relevance: Communication and Cognition*.
- Tager-Flusberg, H. (1999). A psychological approach to understanding the social and language impairments in autism. *International Review of Psychiatry*, 11(4), 325–334. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09540269974203>
- Tager-Flusberg, H. (1999b). A psychological approach to understanding the social and language impairments in autism. *International Review of Psychiatry*, 11(4), 325–334. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09540269974203>
- Tager-Flusberg, H., & Anderson, M. (1991). The development of contingent discourse ability in autistic children. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 32(7), 1123–1134. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-7610.1991.tb00353.x>
- Thomas, J. A. (1983). Cross-Cultural pragmatic failure. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Cross-Cultural-Pragmatic-Failure-Thomas/4fad98208835179896274c56b4b7f39e0b5a1b50?p2df>
- Tzanne, A., Ifantidou, E., & Mitsikopoulou, B. (2009). Raising and assessing pragmatic awareness in L2 academic Language learning. *The International Journal of Learning Annual Review*, 16(9), 297–310. <https://doi.org/10.18848/1447-9494/cgp/v16i09/46549>

Ugwu, Chinyere & Val, Eze & Extension, Kiu Publication. (2023). *Qualitative Research*. 8. 20-35.

Valdespino, J. (2013). Pragmatic language skills inventory. In Springer eBooks (pp. 2326–2327). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-1698-3_503

Van Schalkwyk, G. I., & Dewinter, J. (2020). Qualitative research in the Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 50(7), 2280–2282. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10803-020-04466-8>

Volden, J., & Phillips, L. (2010). Measuring pragmatic language in speakers with autism spectrum Disorders: Comparing the Children’s Communication Checklist—2 and The Test of Pragmatic Language. *American Journal of Speech-Language Pathology*, 19(3), 204–212. [https://doi.org/10.1044/1058-0360\(2010/09-0011](https://doi.org/10.1044/1058-0360(2010/09-0011)

Whitehouse, A. J. O., Line, E. A., Watt, H. J., & Bishop, D. V. M. (2009). Qualitative aspects of developmental language impairment relate to language and literacy outcome in adulthood. *International Journal of Language & Communication Disorders*, 44(4), 489–510. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13682820802708080>

Yoshitake-Strain, S. (1999) Evaluating Six Measures of EFL Learners' Pragmatic Competence. *JALT Journal*, Vol. 21, No.1.

Young, E. C., Diehl, J. J., Morris, D., Hyman, S. L., & Bennetto, L. (2005). The use of two language tests to identify pragmatic language problems in children with autism spectrum disorders. *Language Speech and Hearing Services in Schools*, 36(1), 62–72. [https://doi.org/10.1044/0161-1461\(2005/006](https://doi.org/10.1044/0161-1461(2005/006)

Yule, G. (1996). *Pragmatics*. Oxford University Press.

Zeberlein, C (2014). Examination Of The Accuracy Of The Social Language Development Test For Identification Of Social Language Impairments

APPENDIX

Language Assessment Test

Instructions: Read each scenario carefully and answer the questions or complete the tasks that follow

Task 1: Reading Comprehension

You are reading passages about different situations. As you read, pay attention to details and references made within the text.

Example 1:

"The annual poetry competition starts at around 10:00 a.m. in the conference building. Due to unspecified circumstances, it was postponed for a couple of hours."

Questions:

1. What time does the competition start?
2. Why was it postponed?

Example 2:

"Amin was restless all day, anticipating his fathers visit. When he spotted a familiar Honda in his driveway, he grew visibly tense."

Questions:

1. Who does the Honda belong to?
2. What does Amin's behavior tell you about his feelings about his father?

Example 3:

"Right after Ramadan, Yacine's family always has a big gathering in his grandfather's home. Due to old age, he is diabetic, so he misses out on most of the desserts."

Questions:

1. Why does the family gather at the grandfather's house?
2. Who is diabetic?

Task 2: Analytical Reasoning

You are presented with a series of statements or situations. *Analyze each one and determine whether the conclusion logically follows from the premises provided.*

Example 1:

Premise: "All children of the neighborhood's residents get invited to summer trips."

Conclusion: "Souria got invited to a summer trip. So she must be a child of a resident."

Example 2:

Premise: "If it doesn't stop raining, some of the roads will be blocked"

Conclusion: "Some roads were blocked today, so it must have rained heavily and nonstop."

Example 3:

Premise: "Dates are fruits"

Conclusion: "This fruit is a date, so it must be delicious."

Task 3: Problem-Solving Scenarios

You are presented with a problem or dilemma. *Provide a solution or response based on the information provided.*

Example 1:

Problem: "Your friend expresses frustration over a phone call, but never specifies the reason for it, and simply sounds sad. How would you approach the situation?"

Example 2:

Dilemma: "You accidentally disposed of one of your father's books. What would you do to rectify the situation?"

Example 3:

Challenge: "You are amidst a debate where all involved parties have valid points. How would you decide which speaker has the most validity?"

Task 4: Text-Based Dialogue Analysis

You are presented with a dialogue between characters. *Analyze the dialogue and draw conclusions about the characters' intentions, emotions, or relationships.*

Example 1:

Amina: "Are you okay, Marwa? You look exhausted."

Marwa: "I haven't slept yesterday, but I'll pull through just until the end of the shift."

Amina: "You can go rest in the back. There aren't many customers here now and I can manage on my own."

Example 2:

Ali: "Did you hear about the new job openings at the private school nearby?"

Fatima: "Yes, I did. I'm considering applying for the assistant teacher position. You should too."

Example 3:

Layla: "Don't forget about our teacher's birthday next week."

Omar: "Birthday? I had no idea it was this soon! We should plan something special for her."

Task 5: Critical Reading

You are presented with a passage or article. *Read the text carefully and answer questions or draw conclusions based on the information provided.*

Example 1:

Passage: "The student council was skeptical about the school's new rules. Most students expressed concern and disappointment for the new and strict decisions, while others welcomed the change hesitantly, in hope for a positive turn."

Question:

What can you infer about the students' reactions to the school's new rules?

Example 2:

Article: "Researchers have found a correlation between regular exercise and improved mental health. Exercise not only reduces stress levels but also boosts mood and cognitive function."

Question:

What conclusions can you draw about the benefits of regular exercise based on the information provided?

Abstract:

تهدف هذه الدراسة إلى التحقيق في القدرات اللغوية البراغماتية لدى سبعة مراهقين جزائريين مصابين بالتوحد من وهران، الجزائر. تستخدم الدراسة نهجًا مختلطًا يعتمد على التحليل الموضوعي لدراسة البيانات. يُعد اضطراب طيف التوحد حالة عصبية نمائية تتميز بصعوبات في التفاعل الاجتماعي و سلوكيات متكررة وجامدة. تُعد القدرة البراغماتية، وهي عنصر أساسي في التفاعل الاجتماعي، من القدرات التي تتأثر بالتوحد، مما يجعل الفرد المصاب بالتوحد يواجه صعوبة في فهم اللغة في السياقات الاجتماعية. وقد تم تطوير العديد من طرق التقييم لقياس الكفاءة البراغماتية لدى المصابين بالتوحد، حيث تختبر جوانب مختلفة من هذه القدرة لتوفير ملف سريري للشخص المصاب، بما في ذلك الاختبارات الموحدة. تم تطوير واستخدام اختبار تقييم براغماتي لهذه الدراسة، يأخذ في الاعتبار المفاهيم الأساسية للقدرة البراغماتية، ويستند إلى إعادة تقديم جورج يول للمفاهيم البراغماتية. في النهاية، اتسمت اللغة البراغماتية للمشاركين في الدراسة، كما أظهرت النتائج، بخمسة مواضيع رئيسية: المرجعية والاستدلال، التضمين المنطقي، الأدب والفهم الاجتماعي، فهم الخطاب، والعلاقة مع المعنى العام. أشارت هذه المواضيع إلى تنوع في المهارات والقدرات البراغماتية داخل العينة، وأظهرت أن الأفراد المصابين بالتوحد يمتلكون ملامح براغماتية متنوعة، مما يتحدى فكرة وجود قدرة براغماتية موحدة عبر اضطراب طيف التوحد.

Cette étude a pour objectif d'étudier les capacités linguistiques pragmatiques de sept adolescents autistes algériens d'Oran, en Algérie. L'étude utilise une approche mixte, s'appuyant sur une analyse thématique pour étudier les données. Le trouble du spectre de l'autisme est une affection neurologique caractérisée par des difficultés d'interaction sociale et des comportements répétitifs et rigides. La capacité pragmatique, un élément clé de l'interaction sociale, est notoirement altérée dans l'autisme, ce qui entraîne chez l'individu autiste des difficultés à comprendre le langage dans les contextes sociaux. Plusieurs méthodes d'évaluation ont été développées pour mesurer la compétence pragmatique en TSA, testant différents aspects de la capacité pragmatique afin de fournir un profil clinique pour la personne autiste, y compris des tests d'évaluation standardisés. Un test d'évaluation pragmatique, qui prend en considération les concepts marquants de la capacité pragmatique et qui s'appuie sur la réintroduction des concepts pragmatiques par George Yule, a été élaboré et utilisé pour cette étude spécifique. Au final, le langage pragmatique des participants à l'étude, tel qu'il ressort des résultats, était caractérisé par cinq thèmes principaux : référence et inférence, implication logique, politesse et compréhension sociale, compréhension du discours, et relation avec la signification générale. Les thèmes ont indiqué une variété de compétences et capacités pragmatiques au sein de l'échantillon, et ont montré que les personnes autistes présentent des profils pragmatiques divers, ce qui remet en question la notion d'une capacité pragmatique uniforme dans tout le spectre.